

Protostellar Interferometric Line Survey of the Cygnus-X region (PILS-Cygnus)^{*}

The role of the external environment in setting the chemistry of protostars

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ABSTRACT

Context. Molecular lines are commonly detected towards protostellar sources. However, to get a better understanding of the chemistry of these sources we need unbiased molecular surveys over a wide frequency range for as many sources as possible to shed light on the origin of this chemistry, particularly any influence from the external environment.

Aims. We present results from the PILS-Cygnus survey of ten intermediate- to high-mass protostellar sources in the nearby Cygnus-X complex, through high angular resolution interferometric observations over a wide frequency range.

Methods. Using the Submillimeter Array (SMA), a spectral line survey of ten sources was performed in the frequency range 329–361 GHz, with an angular resolution of $\sim 1''5$, or ~ 2000 AU at a source distance of 1.3 kpc from the Sun. Spectral modelling was performed to identify molecular emission and determine column densities and excitation temperatures for each source. Emission maps were made to study the morphology of emission. Finally, emission properties were compared across the sample.

Results. We detect CH₃OH towards nine of the ten sources, with CH₃OCH₃ and CH₃OCHO towards three sources. We further detect CH₃CN towards four sources. Towards five sources the chemistry is spatially differentiated, meaning that different species peak at different positions and are offset from the peak continuum emission. Low levels of deuteration are detected towards four sources in HDO emission, whereas deuterated complex organic molecule emission is detected towards one source (CH₂DOH towards N63). The chemical properties of each source do not correlate with their position in the Cygnus-X complex, nor do the distance or direction to the nearest OB associations. However, the five sources located in the DR21 filament do appear to show less line emission compared to the five sources outside the filament.

Conclusions. This work shows how important wide frequency coverage observations are combined with high angular resolution observations for studying the protostellar environment. Furthermore, based on the ten sources observed here, the external environment appears to only play a minor role in setting the chemical environment on these small scales (< 2000 AU).

Key words. Astrochemistry; Stars: formation; Stars: protostars; ISM: molecules; Submillimeter: ISM; Astrophysics - Solar and Stellar Astrophysics

References

- Milam, S. N., Savage, C., Brewster, M. A., Ziurys, L. M., & Wyckoff, S. 2005, *ApJ*, 634, 1126
Wilson, T. L. 1999, *Reports on Progress in Physics*, 62, 143

^{*} This document contains the appendices for the published article only. Readers can refer to the article in the journal *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 677, A127 for the full text version, excluding the appendices.

Appendix A: Source sample spectra and emission maps

In this appendix the source sample spectra (Figs. A.1 – A.8) and emission maps (Figs. A.9 – A.16) are shown. The molecular transitions used to produce the molecular emission maps for each source are listed in Tables A.1 – A.10. Readers can refer to the main text for the spectrum and molecular maps for N63.

Fig. A.1. Spectrum towards S26, at the continuum peak. The spectrum shows many molecular lines, with the identified lines marked and labelled.

Fig. A.2. Spectrum towards N12, at the continuum peak of the MM2 core. The brightest lines are marked and labelled.

Fig. A.3. Spectrum towards N53, at the continuum peak of the eastern core. The brightest lines are marked and labelled.

Fig. A.4. Spectrum towards N54, at the continuum peak of the eastern core. The brightest lines are marked and labelled.

Fig. A.5. Spectrum towards N51, at the continuum peak. The brightest lines are marked and labelled.

Fig. A.6. Spectrum towards N38, at the continuum peak. The brightest lines are marked and labelled.

Fig. A.7. Spectrum towards N48, at the continuum peak. The brightest lines are marked and labelled.

Fig. A.8. Spectrum towards S8, at the eastern continuum peak. The brightest lines are marked and labelled.

Fig. A.9. Molecules observed towards S26. The contour levels for both the continuum (grey dashed lines) and molecular emission (coloured) are $3, 6, 12, 24$ and 48σ . The pluses are the molecular emission peak positions derived from 2D Gaussian fits.

Fig. A.10. Molecules observed towards N12. The contour levels for the molecular emission are here 3, 6, 9, 12, and 15σ . The continuum contours are as in Fig. A.9

Fig. A.11. Molecules observed towards N53. The contour levels for the molecular emission are here 3, 6, 9 and 12σ . The continuum contours are as in Fig. A.9

Fig. A.12. Molecules observed towards N54. The contour levels for the molecular emission are here 3σ . The continuum contours are as in Fig. A.9

Fig. A.13. Molecules observed towards N51. The contour levels for the molecular emission are here 3 and 6σ . The continuum contours are as in Fig. A.9

Fig. A.14. Molecules observed towards N38. The contour levels for the molecular emission are here 3 and 6σ . The continuum contours are as in Fig. A.9

Fig. A.15. Molecules observed towards N48. The contour levels for the molecular emission are here 3, 6 and 9σ . The continuum contours are as in Fig. A.9

Fig. A.16. Molecules observed towards S8. The contour levels for the molecular emission are here 3 and 6 σ . The continuum contours are as in Fig. A.9

Table A.1. Gaussian fits for molecular transitions of Complex Organic Molecules, including t-HCOOH and H₂CO, observed towards S26^a.

Molecule	Frequency [GHz]	Transition	Position ["', ''']	I_{peak}^b [Jy beam ⁻¹]	I_{int}^b [Jy beam ⁻¹ km s ⁻¹]	FWHM ^b [km s ⁻¹]	v_{source}^b [km s ⁻¹]
S26							
A-CH ₃ OH	331.5023	11 _{1,-0} – 11 _{0,+0}	(0.15, 0.01)	6.9	31.1	4.1	-4.9
	335.5820	7 _{1,+0} – 6 _{1,+0}	(0.31, 0.02)	5.8	24.3	4.0	-4.6
	336.8651	12 _{1,-0} – 12 _{0,+0}	(0.19, 0.01)	6.7	33.4	4.3	-3.7
	338.4087	7 _{0,+0} – 6 _{0,+0}	(0.15, 0.00)	6.1	41.2	6.1	-4.2
	349.1070	14 _{1,-0} – 11 _{0,+0}	(0.20, -0.09)	6.2	32.0	4.5	-2.9
	355.6029	13 _{0,+0} – 11 _{1,+0}	(0.21, 0.05)	5.9	27.6	4.4	-2.7
	356.0072	15 _{1,-0} – 15 _{0,+0}	(0.23, -0.08)	6.9	33.8	4.2	-4.0
	360.6616	3 _{1,+1} – 4 _{2,+1}	(0.36, 0.18)	4.0	19.9	3.9	-4.4
E-CH ₃ OH	338.1244	7 _{0,0} – 6 _{0,0}	(0.17, 0.04)	6.2	29.2	4.1	-5.5
	338.3446	7 _{-1,0} – 6 _{-1,0}	(0.18, 0.03)	6.5	36.3	4.7	-5.1
	360.8489	11 _{0,0} – 10 _{1,0}	(0.13, 0.12)	5.5	26.8	4.2	-5.3
H ₂ CO	351.7686	5 _{1,5} – 4 _{1,4}	(0.01, -0.16)	10.6	64.8	5.7	-4.2

Notes. ^(a) The transitions listed here, as well as the transitions listed in Tables A.2 and A.3, were relatively isolated and unblended, and were used to make the emission maps shown in Fig. A.9 ^(b) Typical uncertainties on the Gaussian fits are (0'01, 0'01) for the position, 0.3 Jy beam⁻¹ for I_{peak} , 0.8 Jy beam⁻¹ km s⁻¹ for I_{int} , and 0.4 km s⁻¹ for the FWHM and v_{source} .

Table A.2. Gaussian fits for molecular transitions of S-bearing species, observed towards S26.

Molecule	Frequency [GHz]	Transition	Position ["', ''"]	I_{peak} [Jy beam ⁻¹]	I_{int} [Jy beam ⁻¹ km s ⁻¹]	FWHM [km s ⁻¹]	v_{source} [km s ⁻¹]
S26							
CS	342.8828	7 ₀ – 6 ₀	(0.01, 0.07)	11.0	59.9	5.2	-6.4
C ³⁴ S	337.3965	7 ₀ – 6 ₀	(0.02, -0.10)	5.4	25.7	4.5	-4.9
SO	340.7141	8 ₇ – 6 ₆	(0.04, -0.10)	10.7	73.1	6.4	-4.5
	334.4311	8 ₈ – 7 ₇	(0.03, -0.11)	13.0	89.1	6.5	-5.1
	346.5281	8 ₉ – 7 ₈	(0.08, -0.16)	12.8	120.3	9.5	-4.8
³⁴ SO	333.9010	8 ₇ – 7 ₆	(0.10, -0.09)	5.4	28.3	4.6	-5.3
	337.5801	8 ₈ – 7 ₇	(0.04, -0.22)	6.6	39.2	5.3	-5.0
	339.8573	8 ₉ – 7 ₈	(0.10, -0.05)	5.6	31.0	4.8	-4.3
³³ SO	340.8379	8 _{8,7,5} – 7 _{8,6,5}	(0.35, -0.07)	2.1	11.3	4.8	-5.4
	343.0881	8 _{9,9,5} – 7 _{8,8,5}	(0.18, 0.03)	2.6	18.0	5.5	-5.1
SO ₂	331.5802	11 _{6,6} – 12 _{5,7}	(0.16, -0.17)	4.7	23.3	4.1	-5.6
	332.0914	21 _{2,20} – 21 _{1,21}	(0.10, -0.17)	7.4	39.4	4.9	-4.2
	332.5052	4 _{3,1} – 3 _{2,2}	(0.07, -0.19)	9.0	51.2	5.3	-3.6
	336.0892	23 _{3,21} – 23 _{2,22}	(0.09, -0.14)	6.1	35.5	5.2	-4.5
	336.6695	16 _{7,9} – 17 _{6,12}	(0.13, -0.08)	4.1	20.9	4.3	-5.2
	338.3060	18 _{4,14} – 18 _{3,15}	(0.11, -0.09)	8.6	50.9	5.3	-5.7
	340.3164	28 _{2,26} – 28 _{1,27}	(0.14, -0.06)	4.6	27.4	5.3	-4.4
	341.2755	21 _{8,14} – 22 _{7,15}	(0.21, -0.11)	3.4	16.9	4.0	-6.0
	345.4490	26 _{9,17} – 27 _{8,20}	(0.28, -0.17)	1.8	12.7	5.7	-7.6
	346.6522	19 _{1,19} – 18 _{0,18}	(0.08, -0.17)	10.4	67.0	5.9	-6.3
	350.8628	10 _{6,4} – 11 _{5,7}	(0.12, -0.17)	4.7	24.0	4.6	-6.7
	355.0455	12 _{4,8} – 12 _{3,9}	(0.04, -0.12)	9.2	54.1	5.5	-7.4
	356.0406	15 _{7,9} – 16 _{6,10}	(0.05, -0.10)	5.5	31.3	4.8	-5.4
	357.1654	13 _{4,10} – 13 _{3,11}	(0.04, -0.12)	10.0	62.4	5.7	-3.5
	357.2412	15 _{4,12} – 15 _{3,13}	(0.05, -0.12)	9.8	63.3	5.9	-8.3
	357.3876	11 _{4,8} – 11 _{3,9}	(0.02, -0.18)	10.0	59.0	5.5	-5.6
	357.5814	8 _{4,4} – 8 _{3,5}	(0.04, -0.18)	9.2	60.9	6.0	-6.6
	357.8924	7 _{4,4} – 7 _{3,5}	(0.01, -0.14)	10.7	66.6	5.8	-6.5
	357.9258	6 _{4,2} – 6 _{3,3}	(0.05, -0.16)	9.7	60.5	5.5	-7.5
	357.9629	17 _{4,14} – 17 _{3,15}	(0.04, -0.14)	9.5	60.1	5.7	-7.1
	358.0131	5 _{4,2} – 5 _{3,3}	(0.09, -0.12)	9.8	61.4	5.7	-6.6
	358.2156	20 _{0,20} – 19 _{1,19}	(0.08, -0.16)	11.5	75.3	6.0	-7.0
	359.7707	19 _{4,16} – 19 _{3,17}	(0.07, -0.10)	9.1	58.8	5.6	-3.3
360.2904	34 _{5,29} – 34 _{4,30}	(0.08, -0.04)	4.4	26.2	5.6	-7.3	
360.7218	20 _{8,12} – 21 _{7,15}	(0.17, -0.15)	3.6	19.8	4.7	-4.3	
³⁴ SO ₂	330.6676	21 _{2,20} – 21 _{1,21}	(0.32, -0.10)	1.8	7.8	3.7	-7.0
	332.8362	16 _{4,12} – 16 _{3,13}	(0.09, 0.05)	2.3	12.8	4.8	-4.8
	342.2089	5 _{3,3} – 4 _{2,2}	(0.12, -0.00)	2.5	11.3	3.9	-7.1
	342.3320	12 _{4,8} – 12 _{3,9}	(0.31, 0.09)	2.2	13.5	5.0	-6.4
	344.2453	10 _{4,6} – 10 _{3,7}	(0.16, -0.03)	2.9	16.3	4.3	-6.8
	344.5810	19 _{1,19} – 18 _{0,18}	(0.15, -0.08)	4.5	24.6	4.7	-4.5
	357.1022	20 _{0,20} – 19 _{1,19}	(0.10, -0.10)	2.9	18.7	5.6	-7.1
OCS	340.4493	28 – 27	(0.08, -0.12)	3.6	19.4	4.7	-3.5
	352.5996	29 – 28	(0.16, -0.14)	4.5	25.6	5.1	-5.9
H ₂ CS	338.0832	10 _{1,10} – 9 _{1,9}	(0.34, -0.06)	2.1	10.4	4.1	-6.2
	342.9464	10 _{0,10} – 9 _{0,9}	(0.34, 0.01)	1.8	7.8	3.7	-5.1

Notes. Uncertainties are as in Table A.1.

Table A.3. Gaussian fits for molecular transitions of N-bearing species, CO, HCO⁺, SiO and HDO, observed towards S26.

Molecule	Frequency [GHz]	Transition	Position ["', ''']	I_{peak} [Jy beam ⁻¹]	I_{int} [Jy beam ⁻¹ km s ⁻¹]	FWHM [km s ⁻¹]	v_{source} [km s ⁻¹]
S26							
N-bearing species							
CH ₃ CN	330.9126	18 ₅ – 17 ₅	(0.31, -0.13)	2.8	15.2	4.6	-6.3
	330.9698	18 ₄ – 17 ₄	(0.25, -0.22)	3.6	18.4	4.6	-5.9
	331.0143	18 ₃ – 17 ₃	(0.15, -0.08)	5.9	31.1	4.3	-6.0
	331.0461	18 ₂ – 17 ₂	(0.18, -0.15)	5.2	25.4	4.4	-6.3
	349.3933	19 ₃ – 18 ₃	(0.15, -0.04)	6.1	32.7	4.8	-6.9
	349.4268	19 ₂ – 18 ₂	(0.16, -0.11)	5.9	30.8	4.4	-6.2
HNCO	329.6644	15 _{0,15} – 14 _{0,14}	(0.29, -0.04)	3.9	20.2	4.7	-6.4
	350.3330	16 _{1,16} – 15 _{1,15}	(0.18, 0.03)	3.4	18.4	4.7	-8.5
HCN	354.5055	4 – 3	(0.00, 0.03)	11.9	101.8	9.6	-5.3
HC ¹⁵ N	344.2001	4 – 3	(0.10, -0.08)	8.3	50.5	5.4	-4.0
HC ₃ N	336.5201	37 – 36	(0.15, -0.04)	3.0	17.3	5.1	-4.4
	345.6090	38 – 37	(0.19, -0.04)	3.5	21.3	5.3	-7.1
	354.6975	39 – 38	(0.05, -0.27)	2.7	16.6	5.5	-8.7
SiO	347.3306	8 ₀ – 7 ₀	(0.15, 0.10)	1.5	13.8	9.6	-4.7
C ¹⁸ O	329.33050	3 – 2	(0.54, -0.45)	4.0	18.7	5.5	-6.6

Notes. Uncertainties are as in Table A.1.

Table A.4. Molecular transitions of CH₃OH, SO and CH₃CN observed towards N12, used to produce the contour maps shown in Fig. A.10.

Molecule	Frequency [GHz]	Transition	I_{peak}^a [Jy beam ⁻¹]	I_{int}^a [Jy beam ⁻¹ km s ⁻¹]	FWHM ^a [km s ⁻¹]	v_{source}^a [km s ⁻¹]
A-CH ₃ OH	331.5023	11 _{1,-0} – 11 _{0,+0}	1.3	5.8	3.9	16.5
	336.8651	12 _{1,-0} – 12 _{0,+0}	1.1	4.7	4.2	18.1
	341.4156	7 _{1,-0} – 6 _{1,-0}	1.1	3.8	3.9	14.3
	342.7298	13 _{1,-0} – 13 _{0,+0}	0.9	3.0	4.6	15.1
E-CH ₃ OH	338.1244	7 _{0,0} – 6 _{0,0}	1.5	4.7	3.4	16.3
	338.3446	7 _{-1,0} – 6 _{-1,0}	1.6	5.7	3.9	17.1
	338.6149	7 _{1,0} – 6 _{1,0}	1.3	3.3	3.6	16.9
	358.6058	4 _{1,0} – 3 _{0,0}	1.0	4.6	5.0	16.5
SO	340.7141	8 ₇ – 6 ₆	1.1	9.5	6.6	17.8
	344.3106	8 ₈ – 7 ₇	1.4	11.0	6.5	18.7
	346.5281	8 ₉ – 7 ₈	1.6	13.4	6.7	15.4
OCS	340.4493	28 – 27	0.7	2.3	5.0	18.3
	352.5996	29 – 28	0.8	4.5	7.9	15.5
H ₂ CS	338.0832	10 _{1,10} – 9 _{1,9}	1.2	4.9	4.3	17.1
	342.9464	10 _{0,10} – 9 _{0,9}	0.6	2.1	3.9	15.3
CH ₃ CN	331.0143	18 ₃ – 17 ₃	0.8	3.3	4.0	15.9
	331.0461	18 ₂ – 17 ₂	0.7	3.1	5.1	15.7
	331.0652 ^a	18 ₁ – 17 ₁	0.7	6.3	9.7	13.7
	331.0715	18 ₀ – 17 ₀	-	-	-	-
C ¹⁸ O	329.33050	3 – 2	1.5	4.3	3.6	15.1

Notes. ^(a) The two CH₃CN transitions at 331.0652 and 331.0715 are blended and the table entries for these lines therefore represent the values of the two lines combined.

Table A.5. Molecular transitions of CH₃OH, SO and H₂CS observed towards N53, used to produce the contour maps shown in Fig. A.11.

Molecule	Frequency [GHz]	Transition	I_{peak}^a [Jy beam ⁻¹]	I_{int}^a [Jy beam ⁻¹ km s ⁻¹]	FWHM ^a [km s ⁻¹]	v_{source}^a [km s ⁻¹]
A-CH ₃ OH	331.5023	11 _{1,-0} – 11 _{0,+0}	1.1	5.1	4.9	-3.8
	335.5820	7 _{1,+0} – 6 _{1,+0}	1.4	5.3	4.3	-3.1
	336.8651	12 _{1,-0} – 12 _{0,+0}	0.7	5.0	8.3	-2.0
	338.4087	7 _{0,+0} – 6 _{0,+0}	1.6	10.1	6.9	-4.6
	341.4156	7 _{1,-0} – 6 _{1,-0}	1.8	8.4	4.4	-5.3
	349.1070	14 _{1,-0} – 11 _{0,+0}	0.5	3.3	7.8	-5.8
	355.6029	13 _{0,+0} – 11 _{1,+0}	2.0	6.6	3.3	-2.3
E-CH ₃ OH	338.1244	7 _{0,0} – 6 _{0,0}	1.9	7.7	4.3	-3.7
	338.3446	7 _{-1,0} – 6 _{-1,0}	2.5	7.9	4.0	-4.2
	338.7217	7 _{2,0} – 6 _{2,0}	2.7	8.7	3.9	-5.1
SO	340.7141	8 ₇ – 6 ₆	1.7	7.6	4.9	-5.5
	334.4311	8 ₈ – 7 ₇	1.7	9.0	6.1	-3.5
	346.5281	8 ₉ – 7 ₈	2.0	10.5	5.9	-6.4
H ₂ CS	338.0832	10 _{1,10} – 9 _{1,9}	1.3	3.9	4.2	-5.0
	342.9464	10 _{0,10} – 9 _{0,9}	0.5	1.7	5.6	-5.3
	348.5344	10 _{1,9} – 9 _{1,8}	0.7	3.2	4.9	-2.2

Table A.6. Molecular transitions of ¹³CO, CS and H₂CO observed towards N54, used to produce the contour maps shown in Fig. A.12.

Molecule	Frequency [GHz]	Transition	I_{peak}^a [Jy beam ⁻¹]	I_{int}^a [Jy beam ⁻¹ km s ⁻¹]	FWHM ^a [km s ⁻¹]	v_{source}^a [km s ⁻¹]
¹³ CO	330.5880	3 – 2	1.8	4.9	2.2	-9.1
CS	342.8828	7 ₀ – 6 ₀	1.7	7.0	3.6	-5.9
H ₂ CO	351.7686	5 _{1,5} – 4 _{1,4}	1.7	6.0	3.0	-4.4

Table A.7. Molecular transitions of CH₃OH, SO and CS observed towards N51, used to produce the contour maps shown in Fig. A.13.

Molecule	Frequency [GHz]	Transition	I_{peak}^a [Jy beam ⁻¹]	I_{int}^a [Jy beam ⁻¹ km s ⁻¹]	FWHM ^a [km s ⁻¹]	v_{source}^a [km s ⁻¹]
A-CH ₃ OH	331.5023	11 _{1,-0} – 11 _{0,+0}	1.5	3.8	2.6	-2.2
	335.5820	7 _{1,+0} – 6 _{1,+0}	0.5	1.9	6.7	-3.1
	336.8651	12 _{1,-0} – 12 _{0,+0}	1.2	3.5	2.5	-2.7
	338.5129	7 _{2,-0} – 6 _{2,-0}	2.2	5.9	2.2	-3.8
	341.4156	7 _{1,-0} – 6 _{1,-0}	1.0	3.5	4.5	-5.4
SO	340.7141	8 ₇ – 6 ₆	0.8	6.4	7.2	-4.5
	334.4311	8 ₈ – 7 ₇	1.4	7.1	4.8	-4.1
	346.5281	8 ₉ – 7 ₈	1.1	9.4	9.1	-6.2
CS	342.8828	7 ₀ – 6 ₀	2.4	12.9	4.4	1.2

Table A.8. Molecular transitions of CH₃OH, SO and CS observed towards N38, used to produce the contour maps shown in Fig. A.14.

Molecule	Frequency [GHz]	Transition	I_{peak}^a [Jy beam ⁻¹]	I_{int}^a [Jy beam ⁻¹ km s ⁻¹]	FWHM ^a [km s ⁻¹]	v_{source}^a [km s ⁻¹]
A-CH ₃ OH	335.5820	7 _{1,+0} – 6 _{1,+0}	0.7	2.2	4.6	0.2
	336.8651	12 _{1,-0} – 12 _{0,+0}	0.4	2.1	7.6	-4.3
	338.4087	7 _{0,+0} – 6 _{0,+0}	1.4	6.0	5.2	-3.5
	341.4156	7 _{1,-0} – 6 _{1,-0}	0.9	4.0	5.7	-2.7
	342.7298	13 _{1,-0} – 13 _{0,+0}	0.5	3.0	3.8	-0.8
E-CH ₃ OH	338.1244	7 _{0,0} – 6 _{0,0}	0.9	1.8	5.3	0.5
	338.3446	7 _{-1,0} – 6 _{-1,0}	1.2	5.7	5.6	-3.0
	338.6149	7 _{1,0} – 6 _{1,0}	0.7	3.4	4.4	0.2
	338.7217	7 _{2,0} – 6 _{2,0}	1.2	4.8	4.4	-2.1
	358.6058	4 _{1,0} – 3 _{0,0}	0.6	3.7	6.8	-0.6
SO	340.7141	8 ₇ – 6 ₆	0.3	1.5	12.6	1.1
	334.4311	8 ₈ – 7 ₇	0.6	3.4	12.4	1.3
	346.5281	8 ₉ – 7 ₈	0.7	4.0	13.7	0.5
CS	342.8828	7 ₀ – 6 ₀	1.9	7.5	4.1	0.2

Table A.9. Molecular transitions of CH₃OH and SO observed towards N48, used to produce the contour maps shown in Fig. A.15.

Molecule	Frequency [GHz]	Transition	I_{peak}^a [Jy beam ⁻¹]	I_{int}^a [Jy beam ⁻¹ km s ⁻¹]	FWHM ^a [km s ⁻¹]	v_{source}^a [km s ⁻¹]
A-CH ₃ OH	331.5023	11 _{1,-0} – 11 _{0,+0}	0.5	0.5	6.2	-2.1
	335.5820	7 _{1,+0} – 6 _{1,+0}	0.8	2.6	4.9	-4.8
	338.4087	7 _{0,+0} – 6 _{0,+0}	2.5	8.7	5.3	-8.4
	341.4156	7 _{1,-0} – 6 _{1,-0}	1.3	4.1	-4.0	-10.3
E-CH ₃ OH	338.1244	7 _{0,0} – 6 _{0,0}	0.7	5.6	10.3	-7.8
	338.3446	7 _{-1,0} – 6 _{-1,0}	2.3	7.4	4.8	-8.1
	338.7217	7 _{2,0} – 6 _{2,0}	1.0	5.2	4.6	-4.4
	358.6058	4 _{1,0} – 3 _{0,0}	0.5	2.9	10.7	-7.9
SO	340.7141	8 ₇ – 6 ₆	0.6	5.4	6.8	-5.3
	334.4311	8 ₈ – 7 ₇	0.6	4.2	8.0	-5.8
	346.5281	8 ₉ – 7 ₈	0.8	5.9	8.0	-8.0

Table A.10. Molecular transitions of CH₃OH and SO observed towards S8, used to produce the contour maps shown in Fig. A.16.

Molecule	Frequency [GHz]	Transition	I_{peak}^a [Jy beam ⁻¹]	I_{int}^a [Jy beam ⁻¹ km s ⁻¹]	FWHM ^a [km s ⁻¹]	v_{source}^a [km s ⁻¹]
A-CH ₃ OH	331.5023	11 _{1,-0} – 11 _{0,+0}	0.5	0.5	6.2	-2.1
	335.5820	7 _{1,+0} – 6 _{1,+0}	0.8	2.6	4.9	-4.8
	338.4087	7 _{0,+0} – 6 _{0,+0}	2.5	8.7	5.3	-8.4
	341.4156	7 _{1,-0} – 6 _{1,-0}	1.3	4.1	-4.0	-10.3
E-CH ₃ OH	338.1244	7 _{0,0} – 6 _{0,0}	0.7	5.6	10.3	-7.8
	338.3446	7 _{-1,0} – 6 _{-1,0}	2.3	7.4	4.8	-8.1
	338.7217	7 _{2,0} – 6 _{2,0}	1.0	5.2	4.6	-4.4
	358.6058	4 _{1,0} – 3 _{0,0}	0.5	2.9	10.7	-7.9
SO	340.7141	8 ₇ – 6 ₆	0.6	5.4	6.8	-5.3
	334.4311	8 ₈ – 7 ₇	0.6	4.2	8.0	-5.8
	346.5281	8 ₉ – 7 ₈	0.8	5.9	8.0	-8.0

Appendix B: Source sample column densities

The derived values for the source sample obtained from synthetic spectrum fitting using the software package CASSIS are presented in this appendix, in Tables B.1 – B.8 (readers are referred to Table 6 in the main text for values obtained for N63). The parameters used in the fitting were the column density (N), excitation temperature (T_{ex}), source velocity (v_{peak}) and line width (FWHM). These column densities are shown relative to CH_3OH in Fig. B.1.

Fig. B.1. Relative abundances to CH₃OH for the source sample. White and black arrows represent upper and lower limits respectively, while black bars represent uncertainties.

Table B.1. Column densities, excitation temperatures, FWHM and v_{peak} derived at the continuum peak position of S26^a

Molecule	Column density [cm ⁻²]	T_{ex} [K]	FWHM [km s ⁻¹]	v_{peak} [km s ⁻¹]
COMs and O-bearing species				
CH ₃ OH ^b	1.2 (0.2) ^c × 10 ¹⁸	100 (25) ^c	4.0	-5.5
¹³ CH ₃ OH	1.8 (0.3) × 10 ¹⁶	100 (25)	4.0	-5.5
CH ₃ ¹⁸ OH ^c	<1.0 × 10 ¹⁶	100	4.0	-5.5
CH ₂ DOH ^c	<1.0 × 10 ¹⁶	100	4.0	-5.5
C ₂ H ₅ OH ^c	<1.5 × 10 ¹⁶	100	4.0	-5.5
CH ₃ OCHO	3.5 (0.5) × 10 ¹⁶	100 (25)	4.0	-5.5
CH ₃ OCH ₃	2.6 (0.5) × 10 ¹⁶	100 (25)	4.0	-5.5
t-HCOOH	7.0 (1.0) × 10 ¹⁵	190 (60)	4.0	-5.5
c-HCOOH ^c	<1.0 × 10 ¹⁵	190	4.0	-5.5
HDO ^d	3.3 (1.0) × 10 ¹⁶	100 (25)	4.0	-5.5
S-bearing species				
SO ^b	3.5 (0.9) × 10 ¹⁷	120 (40)	4.0	-5.0
³³ SO	3.6 (1.0) × 10 ¹⁵	120 (40)	4.0	-5.0
³⁴ SO	1.6 (0.4) × 10 ¹⁶	120 (20)	3.5	-5.0
SO ₂ ^b	5.9 (0.7) × 10 ¹⁷	120 (20)	4.0	-5.0
³³ SO ₂ ^c	<7.0 × 10 ¹⁵	120	4.0	-5.0
³⁴ SO ₂	2.6 (0.3) × 10 ¹⁶	120 (20)	4.0	-5.0
OCS ^b	1.4 (0.2) × 10 ¹⁷	100 (50)	4.0	-4.5
OC ³⁴ S	6.4 (1.0) × 10 ¹⁵	100 (50)	4.0	-4.5
H ₂ CS	2.6 (0.5) × 10 ¹⁵	130 (40)	4.0	-5.0
N-bearing species				
CH ₃ CN, $v_8=1$	2.0 (0.5) × 10 ¹⁶	140 (20)	4.5	-5.0
¹³ CH ₃ CN ^e	< 5.0 × 10 ¹⁴	120	5.0	-5.5
HNCO	1.0 (0.4) × 10 ¹⁶	140 (30)	4.5	-5.5
HC ₃ N	1.0 (0.2) × 10 ¹⁴	140 (20)	4.5	-5.5

Notes. ^(a) Values are derived from synthetic spectrum fitting with CASSIS, with the assumption of LTE. ^(b) Column densities for optically thick lines derived using local ISM ratios (Wilson 1999; Milam et al. 2005) ^(c) Uncertainties on N and T_{ex} are in parenthesis next to the derived values. ^(d) Upper limits were determined by setting T_{ex} , FWHM, and v_{peak} , equal to that derived for CH₃OH and SO, for the O- and S-bearing species respectively. ^(e) To estimate a column density for HDO, the excitation temperature and line width of methanol was assumed.

Table B.2. Column densities, excitation temperatures, FWHM and v_{peak} derived at the continuum peak position of N12-MM2^a

Molecule	Column density [cm ⁻²]	T_{ex} [K]	FWHM [km s ⁻¹]	v_{peak} [km s ⁻¹]
COMs and O-bearing species				
CH ₃ OH ^b	$5.5 (0.2) \times 10^{17}$	150 (50)	3.5	16.0
¹³ CH ₃ OH ^c	$8.0 (0.3) \times 10^{15}$	150 (50)	3.5	16.0
CH ₃ ¹⁸ OH	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	3.5	16.0
CH ₂ DOH	$<2.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	3.5	16.0
C ₂ H ₅ OH	$<2.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	3.5	16.0
CH ₃ OCHO	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	3.5	16.0
CH ₃ OCH ₃	$<2.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	3.5	16.0
t-HCOOH	$<2.0 \times 10^{15}$	150	3.5	16.0
c-HCOOH	$<2.0 \times 10^{14}$	150	3.5	16.0
HDO ^d	$2.0 (1.0) \times 10^{16}$	150	3.5	16.0
S-bearing species				
SO ^b	$1.1 (0.2) \times 10^{16}$	250 (50)	3.0	15.0
³³ SO ^c	$<5.0 \times 10^{14}$	250	3.0	15.0
³⁴ SO	$5.0 (1.0) \times 10^{14}$	250 (50)	3.0	15.0
SO ₂ ^b	$>5.0 \times 10^{15}$	250	3.0	15.0
³³ SO ₂	$<5.0 \times 10^{15}$	250	3.0	15.0
³⁴ SO ₂	$<5.0 \times 10^{15}$	250	3.0	15.0
OCS ^b	$3.3 (1.0) \times 10^{16}$	200 (100)	4.0	16.0
OC ³⁴ S	$1.5 (0.5) \times 10^{15}$	200 (100)	4.0	16.0
H ₂ CS	$2.0 (0.5) \times 10^{15}$	100 (50)	4.0	16.0
N-bearing species				
CH ₃ CN, $v_8=1$	$2.0 (1.0) \times 10^{15}$	250 (50)	4.0	15.5
¹³ CH ₃ CN ^d	$<2.0 \times 10^{14}$	250	4.0	15.5
HNCO	$<2.0 \times 10^{15}$	250	4.0	15.5
HC ₃ N	$<2.0 \times 10^{14}$	250	4.0	15.5
HC ¹⁵ N	$1.0 (0.3) \times 10^{14}$	250 (50)	3.5	16.0

Notes. ^(a) Values are derived from synthetic spectrum fitting with CASSIS, with the assumption of LTE. ^(b) Column densities for optically thick lines derived using local ISM ratios (Wilson 1999; Milam et al. 2005). In the case of SO₂ only a lower limit is given since ³⁴SO₂ was not detected. ^(c) Upper limits were determined by setting T_{ex} , FWHM, and v_{peak} , equal to that derived for CH₃OH and SO, for the O- and S-bearing species respectively. ^(d) To estimate a column density for HDO, the excitation temperature and line width of methanol was assumed.

Table B.3. Column densities, excitation temperatures, FWHM and v_{peak} derived at the continuum peak position of N53^a

Molecule	Column density [cm ⁻²]	T_{ex} [K]	FWHM [km s ⁻¹]	v_{peak} [km s ⁻¹]
COMs and O-bearing species				
CH ₃ OH	$>1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.5	-5.0
¹³ CH ₃ OH	$<5.0 \times 10^{15}$	150	4.5	-5.0
CH ₃ ¹⁸ OH	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.5	-5.0
CH ₂ DOH	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	100	4.5	-5.0
C ₂ H ₅ OH	$<2.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.5	-5.0
CH ₃ OCHO	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.5	-5.0
CH ₃ OCH ₃	$<2.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.5	-5.0
t-HCOOH	$<5.0 \times 10^{15}$	150	4.5	-5.0
c-HCOOH	$<1.0 \times 10^{15}$	150	4.5	-5.0
HDO	$<3.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.5	-5.0
S-bearing species				
SO	$>3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.5	-4.5
³³ SO	$<5.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.5	-4.5
³⁴ SO	$<5.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.5	-4.5
SO ₂	$<6.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.5	-4.5
³³ SO ₂	$<3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.5	-4.5
³⁴ SO ₂	$<3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.5	-4.5
OCS	$>5.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.5	-5.5
OC ³⁴ S	$<3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.5	-4.5
H ₂ CS	$<3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.5	-4.5
N-bearing species				
CH ₃ CN	$<1.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.5	-4.5
¹³ CH ₃ CN	$<2.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.5	-4.5
HNCO	$<3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.5	-4.5
HC ₃ N	$<2.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.5	-4.5
HC ¹⁵ N	$<1.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.5	-4.5

Notes. ^(a) Values are derived from synthetic spectrum fitting with CASSIS, with the assumption of LTE. Only CH₃OH and SO are detected, but with no isotopologues detected, only lower limits are derived. Upper limits are derived for all other molecules.

Table B.4. Column densities, excitation temperatures, FWHM and v_{peak} derived at the continuum peak position of N54^a

Molecule	Column density [cm ⁻²]	T_{ex} [K]	FWHM [km s ⁻¹]	v_{peak} [km s ⁻¹]
COMs and O-bearing species				
CH ₃ OH ^b	<7.0 × 10 ¹⁷	150	4.0	-5.5
¹³ CH ₃ OH ^b	<1.0 × 10 ¹⁶	150	4.0	-5.5
CH ₃ ¹⁸ OH	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁶	150	4.0	-5.5
CH ₂ DOH	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁶	150	4.0	-5.5
C ₂ H ₅ OH	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁶	150	4.0	-5.5
CH ₃ OCHO	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁶	150	4.0	-5.5
CH ₃ OCH ₃	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁶	150	4.0	-5.5
t-HCOOH	<6.0 × 10 ¹⁵	150	4.0	-5.5
c-HCOOH	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁵	150	4.0	-5.5
HDO	<3.0 × 10 ¹⁶	150	4.0	-5.5
S-bearing species				
SO	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁶	200	4.5	-5.5
³³ SO	<5.0 × 10 ¹⁴	200	4.5	-5.5
³⁴ SO	<8.0 × 10 ¹⁴	200	4.5	-5.5
SO ₂	<5.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.5	-5.5
³³ SO ₂	<4.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.5	-5.5
³⁴ SO ₂	<4.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.5	-5.5
OCS	<4.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.5	-5.5
OC ³⁴ S	<4.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.5	-5.5
H ₂ CS	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.5	-5.5
N-bearing species				
CH ₃ CN	<5.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.5	-5.5
¹³ CH ₃ CN	<3.0 × 10 ¹⁴	200	4.5	-5.5
HNCO	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.5	-5.5
HC ₃ N	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁴	200	4.5	-5.5
HC ¹⁵ N	<1.0 × 10 ¹⁴	200	4.5	-5.5

Notes. ^(a) Values are derived from synthetic spectrum fitting with CASSIS, with the assumption of LTE. ^(b) No COMs were detected, and only upper limits are given. In the case of CH₃OH, and SO, the upper limits given are derived from the ¹³C and ³⁴S isotopologues, respectively. We assumed T_{ex} of 150 K for the O-bearing species, and 200 K for S- and N-bearing species, which is an average of those derived for N30, N12, N63 and S26.

Table B.5. Column densities, excitation temperatures, FWHM and v_{peak} derived at the continuum peak position of N51^a

Molecule	Column density [cm ⁻²]	T_{ex} [K]	FWHM [km s ⁻¹]	v_{peak} [km s ⁻¹]
COMs and O-bearing species				
CH ₃ OH	$>4.0 \times 10^{15}$	150	4.0	-4.5
¹³ CH ₃ OH	$<5.0 \times 10^{15}$	150	4.0	-4.5
CH ₃ ¹⁸ OH	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-4.5
CH ₂ DOH	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-4.5
C ₂ H ₅ OH	$<2.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-4.5
CH ₃ OCHO	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-4.5
CH ₃ OCH ₃	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-4.5
t-HCOOH	$<5.0 \times 10^{15}$	150	4.0	-4.5
c-HCOOH	$<1.0 \times 10^{15}$	150	4.0	-4.5
HDO	$<4.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-4.5
S-bearing species				
SO	$>3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-4.5
³³ SO	$<5.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-4.5
³⁴ SO	$<6.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-4.5
SO ₂	$<6.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-4.5
³³ SO ₂	$<3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-4.5
³⁴ SO ₂	$<3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-4.5
OCS	$<3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-4.5
OC ³⁴ S	$<2.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-4.5
H ₂ CS	$<2.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-4.5
N-bearing species				
CH ₃ CN	$<6.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.5	-4.5
¹³ CH ₃ CN	$<3.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.5	-4.5
HNCO	$<3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.5	-4.5
HC ₃ N	$<2.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.5	-4.5
HC ¹⁵ N	$<1.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.5	-4.5

Notes. ^(a) Values are derived from synthetic spectrum fitting with CASSIS, with the assumption of LTE. Only CH₃OH and SO are detected, but with no isotopologues detected, only lower limits are derived. Upper limits are derived for all other molecules, using average values for T_{ex} derived from the sources where these molecules are detected.

Table B.6. Column densities, excitation temperatures, FWHM and v_{peak} derived at the continuum peak position of N38^a

Molecule	Column density [cm ⁻²]	T_{ex} [K]	FWHM [km s ⁻¹]	v_{peak} [km s ⁻¹]
COMs and O-bearing species				
CH ₃ OH	$>1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-1.0
¹³ CH ₃ OH	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-1.0
CH ₃ ¹⁸ OH	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-1.0
CH ₂ DOH	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-1.0
C ₂ H ₅ OH	$<2.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-1.0
CH ₃ OCHO	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-1.0
CH ₃ OCH ₃	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-1.0
t-HCOOH	$<6.0 \times 10^{15}$	150	4.0	-1.0
c-HCOOH	$<1.0 \times 10^{15}$	150	4.0	-1.0
HDO	$<4.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-1.0
S-bearing species				
SO	$>2.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-1.0
³³ SO	$<5.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-1.0
³⁴ SO	$<6.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-1.0
SO ₂	$<6.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-1.0
³³ SO ₂	$<3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-1.0
³⁴ SO ₂	$<3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-1.0
OCS	$<4.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-1.0
OC ³⁴ S	$<3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-1.0
H ₂ CS	$1.0 (0.5) \times 10^{15}$	100 (50)	3.5	-1.0
N-bearing species				
CH ₃ CN	$<5.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-1.0
¹³ CH ₃ CN	$<2.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-1.0
HNCO	$<5.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-1.0
HC ₃ N	$<2.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-1.0
HC ¹⁵ N	$<1.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-1.0

Notes. ^(a) Values are derived from synthetic spectrum fitting with CASSIS, with the assumption of LTE. Only CH₃OH and SO are detected, but with no isotopologues detected, only lower limits are derived. Upper limits are derived for all other molecules, using average values for T_{ex} derived from the sources where these molecules are detected.

Table B.7. Column densities, excitation temperatures, FWHM and v_{peak} derived at the continuum peak position of N48^a

Molecule	Column density [cm ⁻²]	T_{ex} [K]	FWHM [km s ⁻¹]	v_{peak} [km s ⁻¹]
COMs and O-bearing species				
CH ₃ OH	$>1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-5.0
¹³ CH ₃ OH	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-5.0
CH ₃ ¹⁸ OH	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-5.0
CH ₂ DOH	$<2.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-5.0
C ₂ H ₅ OH	$<2.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-5.0
CH ₃ OCHO	$<1.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-5.0
CH ₃ OCH ₃	$<2.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-5.0
t-HCOOH	$<5.0 \times 10^{15}$	150	4.0	-5.0
c-HCOOH	$<1.0 \times 10^{15}$	150	4.0	-5.0
HDO	$<3.0 \times 10^{16}$	150	4.0	-5.0
S-bearing species				
SO	$>1.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-5.0
³³ SO	$<5.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-5.0
³⁴ SO	$<5.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-5.0
SO ₂	$<5.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-5.0
³³ SO ₂	$<3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-5.0
³⁴ SO ₂	$<3.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-5.0
OCS	$<4.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-5.0
OC ³⁴ S	$<2.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-5.0
H ₂ CS	$<2.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-5.0
N-bearing species				
CH ₃ CN	$<5.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-5.0
¹³ CH ₃ CN	$<3.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-5.0
HNCO	$<2.0 \times 10^{15}$	200	4.0	-5.0
HC ₃ N	$<2.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-5.0
HC ¹⁵ N	$<2.0 \times 10^{14}$	200	4.0	-5.0

Notes. ^(a) Values are derived from synthetic spectrum fitting with CASSIS, with the assumption of LTE. Only CH₃OH and SO are detected, but with no isotopologues detected, only lower limits are derived. Upper limits are derived for all other molecules.

Table B.8. Column densities, excitation temperatures, FWHM and v_{peak} derived at the continuum peak position of S8^a

Molecule	Column density [cm ⁻²]	T_{ex} [K]	FWHM [km s ⁻¹]	v_{peak} [km s ⁻¹]
COMs and O-bearing species				
CH ₃ OH	<8.0 × 10 ¹⁵	150	4.0	1.0
¹³ CH ₃ OH	<6.0 × 10 ¹⁵	150	4.0	1.0
CH ₃ ¹⁸ OH	<1.0 × 10 ¹⁶	150	4.0	1.0
CH ₂ DOH	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁶	150	4.0	1.0
C ₂ H ₅ OH	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁶	150	4.0	1.0
CH ₃ OCHO	<1.0 × 10 ¹⁶	150	4.0	1.0
CH ₃ OCH ₃	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁶	150	4.0	1.0
H ₂ CO	>2.0 × 10 ¹⁵	150	4.0	1.0
H ₂ ¹³ CO	<1.0 × 10 ¹⁵	150	4.0	1.0
t-HCOOH	<5.0 × 10 ¹⁵	150	4.0	1.0
c-HCOOH	<1.0 × 10 ¹⁵	150	4.0	1.0
HDO	<4.0 × 10 ¹⁶	150	4.0	1.0
S-bearing species				
SO	>1.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.0	1.0
³³ SO	<5.0 × 10 ¹⁴	200	4.0	1.0
³⁴ SO	<5.0 × 10 ¹⁴	200	4.0	1.0
SO ₂	<6.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.0	1.0
³³ SO ₂	<4.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.0	1.0
³⁴ SO ₂	<4.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.0	1.0
OCS	<4.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.0	1.0
OC ³⁴ S	<3.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.0	1.0
H ₂ CS	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.0	1.0
N-bearing species				
CH ₃ CN	<3.0 × 10 ¹⁴	200	4.0	1.0
¹³ CH ₃ CN	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁴	200	4.0	1.0
HNCO	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁵	200	4.0	1.0
HC ₃ N	<2.0 × 10 ¹⁴	200	4.0	1.0
HC ¹⁵ N	<1.0 × 10 ¹⁴	200	4.0	1.0

Notes. ^(a) Values are derived from synthetic spectrum fitting with CASSIS, with the assumption of LTE. Only CH₃OH and SO are detected, but with no isotopologues detected, only lower limits are derived. Upper limits are derived for all other molecules.

Appendix C: Molecular line plots

In this Appendix the plots of all the lines for each of the molecules listed in Tables A.1 – A.10 are presented. In all the plots, the model is over-plotted in blue over the observed spectrum in black. Only lines detected above 3σ ~10 K intensity are shown.

Fig. C.1. Detected CH_3OH lines towards S26. Since the lines are optically thick, we used $^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (multiplied by the local ISM value of $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C} = 68$) to derive a column density of $1.2 (0.2) \times 10^{18} \text{cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. C.2. Detected CH_3OH lines towards S26. Since the lines are optically thick, we used $^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (multiplied by the local ISM value of $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C} = 68$) to derive a column density of $1.2 (0.2) \times 10^{18} \text{cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. C.3. Detected CH_3OH lines towards S26. Since the lines are optically thick, we used $^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (multiplied by the local ISM value of $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C} = 68$) to derive a column density of $1.2 (0.2) \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. C.4. Detected $^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $1.8 (0.3)\times 10^{16}\text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 100 (25)K.

Fig. C.5. Detected CH₃OCHO lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlapped on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of 3.5 (0.5)×10¹⁶cm⁻², with excitation temperature 100 (25)K.

Fig. C.6. Detected CH_3OCHO lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlapped on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $3.5 (0.5) \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 100 (25)K.

Fig. C.7. Detected CH_3OCHO lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $3.5 (0.5) \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 100 (25)K.

Fig. C.8. Detected CH_3OCHO lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlapped on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $2.6(0.5)\times 10^{16}\text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 100 (25)K.

Fig. C.9. Detected CH_3OCH_3 lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overplotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $2.6 (0.5)\times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 100 (25)K.

Fig. C.10. Detected t-HCOOH lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overplotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $7.0 (1.0)\times 10^{15} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 190 (60)K.

Fig. C.11. Since SO lines are optically thick, we used ^{34}SO (multiplied by the local ISM value of $^{32}\text{S}/^{34}\text{S} = 22$) to derive a column density of $3.5 (0.9) \times 10^{17} \text{cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. C.12. Detected ^{33}SO lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $3.6 (1.0) \times 10^{15} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 120 (40)K.

Fig. C.13. Detected ^{34}SO lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overplotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $1.6 (0.4)\times 10^{16}\text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 120 (20)K.

Fig. C.14. Since SO₂ lines are optically thick, we used ³⁴SO₂ (multiplied by the local ISM value of ³²S/³⁴S = 22) to derive a column density of 5.9 (0.7) × 10¹⁷ cm⁻².

Fig. C.15. Since SO_2 lines are optically thick, we used $^{34}\text{SO}_2$ (multiplied by the local ISM value of $^{32}\text{S}/^{34}\text{S} = 22$) to derive a column density of $5.9 (0.7) \times 10^{17} \text{cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. C.16. Detected $^{34}\text{SO}_2$ lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlapped on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $2.6 (0.3) \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 120 (20)K.

Fig. C.17. Since OCS lines are optically thick, we used OC³⁴S (multiplied by the local ISM value of $^{32}\text{S}/^{34}\text{S} = 22$) to derive a column density of $1.4 (0.2)\times 10^{17}\text{cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. C.18. Detected OC³⁴S lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overplotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $6.4 (1.0)\times 10^{15}\text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 100 (50)K.

Fig. C.19. Detected H₂CS lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overplotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $2.6 (0.2)\times 10^{15}\text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 130 (40)K.

Fig. C.20. Detected $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}, v=0$ lines towards S26. Since the lines are optically thick, we used $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}, v=1$ to derive a column density of $2.0 (0.5) \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 140 (20)K.

Fig. C.21. Detected $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}, v_8=1$ lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $2.0 (0.5) \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 140 (20)K.

Fig. C.22. Detected HNC lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $1.0 (0.4) \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 140 (30)K.

Fig. C.23. Detected HC₃N lines towards S26. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overplotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $1.0 (0.2) \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 140 (20)K.

Fig. C.24. Detected CH₃OH lines towards N12. Since the lines are optically thick, we used ¹³CH₃OH (multiplied by the local ISM value of ¹²C/¹³C = 68) to derive a column density of 5.5 (0.2)×10¹⁷cm⁻².

Fig. C.25. Detected CH_3OH lines towards N12. Since the lines are optically thick, we used $^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (multiplied by the local ISM value of $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C} = 68$) to derive a column density of $5.5 (0.2) \times 10^{17} \text{cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. C.26. Detected CH₃OH lines towards N12. Since the lines are optically thick, we used ¹³CH₃OH (multiplied by the local ISM value of ¹²C/¹³C = 68) to derive a column density of 5.5 (0.2)×10¹⁷cm⁻².

Fig. C.27. Detected $^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ lines towards N12. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlapped on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $8.0 (0.3) \times 10^{15} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 150 (25)K.

Fig. C.28. Detected SO lines towards N12. Since the lines are optically thick, we used ^{34}S (multiplied by the local ISM value of $^{32}\text{S}/^{34}\text{S} = 22$) to derive a column density of $1.1 (0.2)\times 10^{16}\text{cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. C.29. Detected ^{34}S O lines towards N12. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $3.5 (0.5)\times 10^{16}\text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 250 (50)K.

Fig. C.30. Detected OCS lines towards N12. Since the lines are optically thick, we used OC^{34}S (multiplied by the local ISM value of $^{32}\text{S}/^{34}\text{S} = 22$) to derive a column density of $3.3 (1.0)\times 10^{16}\text{cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. C.31. Detected OC^{34}S lines towards N12. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $1.5 (0.5)\times 10^{15}\text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 200 (100)K.

Fig. C.32. Detected H₂CS lines towards N12. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $2.0 (0.5) \times 10^{15} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 100 (50)K.

Fig. C.33. Detected CH₃CN lines towards N12. Since the lines are optically thick, we used the higher vibration transitions CH₃CN, $v_8 = 1$ to derive a column density of $2.0 (1.0) \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. C.34. Detected $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}, v_8 = 1$ lines towards N12. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overplotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $2.0 (1.0) \times 10^{15} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 250 (50)K.

Fig. C.35. Detected CH₃OH lines towards N63. Since the lines are optically thick, we used ¹³CH₃OH (multiplied by the local ISM value of ¹²C/¹³C = 68) to derive a column density of 5.0 (0.2)×10¹⁷cm⁻².

Fig. C.36. Detected CH_3OH lines towards N63. Since the lines are optically thick, we used $^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (multiplied by the local ISM value of $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C} = 68$) to derive a column density of $5.0 (0.2) \times 10^{17} \text{cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. C.37. Detected CH_3OH lines towards N63. Since the lines are optically thick, we used $^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (multiplied by the local ISM value of $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C} = 68$) to derive a column density of $5.0 (0.2) \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. C.38. Detected $^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ lines towards N63. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $5.8 (0.3)\times 10^{15}\text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 120 (50)K.

Fig. C.39. Detected CH₂DOH lines towards N63. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $1.5(0.4)\times 10^{16}\text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 150(40)K.

Fig. C.40. Detected CH₃OCHO lines towards N63. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overplotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $1.2(0.4) \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 120 (40)K.

Fig. C.41. Detected CH_3OCHO lines towards N63. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlapped on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $1.2 (0.4) \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 120 (40)K.

Fig. C.42. Detected CH_3OCHO lines towards N63. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overplotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $1.2 (0.4) \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 120 (40)K.

Fig. C.43. Detected CH_3OCHO lines towards N63. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overplotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $1.4 (0.4) \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 120 (40)K.

Fig. C.44. Detected CH_3OCH_3 lines towards N63. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overplotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $1.4 (0.4) \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 120 (40)K.

Fig. C.45. Since SO lines are optically thick, we used ^{34}SO (multiplied by the local ISM value of $^{32}\text{S}/^{34}\text{S} = 22$) to derive a column density of $1.2 (0.3) \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. C.46. Detected ^{34}SO lines towards N63. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overplotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $5.5 (1.0) \times 10^{14} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 250 (50)K.

Fig. C.47. Since OCS lines are optically thick, we used OC^{34}S (multiplied by the local ISM value of $^{32}\text{S}/^{34}\text{S} = 22$) to derive a column density of $3.3 (1.1) \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. C.48. Detected OC^{34}S lines towards N63. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $1.5 (0.5) \times 10^{15} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 100 (30)K.

Fig. C.49. Detected H_2CS lines towards N63. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $3.0 (1.0) \times 10^{15} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 150 (40)K.

Fig. C.50. Detected $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}, v=0$ lines towards N64. Since the lines are optically thick, we used $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}, v=1$ to derive a column density of $5.0 (3.0) \times 10^{15} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 120 (20)K.

Fig. C.51. Detected $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}, v=1$ lines towards N64. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overplotted on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $5.0 (3.0) \times 10^{15} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 120 (20)K.

Fig. C.52. Detected CH₃OH lines towards N53. Based on results from the source sample we conclude that the detected lines are optically thick, and since no isotopologues were detected we were not able to derive a column density for this molecule.

Fig. C.53. Detected CH_3OH lines towards N53. Based on results from the source sample we conclude that the detected lines are optically thick, and since no isotopologues were detected we were not able to derive a column density for this molecule.

Fig. C.54. Detected SO lines towards N53. Based on results from the source sample we conclude that the detected lines are optically thick, and since no isotopologues were detected we were not able to derive a column density for this molecule.

Fig. C.55. Detected OCS lines towards N53. Based on results from the source sample we conclude that the detected lines are optically thick, and since no isotopologues were detected we were not able to derive a column density for this molecule.

Fig. C.56. Detected CH₃OH lines towards N51. Based on results from the source sample we conclude that the detected lines are optically thick, and since no isotopologues were detected we were not able to derive a column density for this molecule.

Fig. C.57. Detected CH_3OH lines towards N51. Based on results from the source sample we conclude that the detected lines are optically thick, and since no isotopologues were detected we were not able to derive a column density for this molecule.

Fig. C.58. Detected SO lines towards N51. Based on results from the source sample we conclude that the detected lines are optically thick, and since no isotopologues were detected we were not able to derive a column density for this molecule.

Fig. C.59. Detected CH₃OH lines towards N38. Based on results from the source sample we conclude that the detected lines are optically thick, and since no isotopologues were detected we were not able to derive a column density for this molecule.

Fig. C.60. Detected CH₃OH lines towards N38. Based on results from the source sample we conclude that the detected lines are optically thick, and since no isotopologues were detected we were not able to derive a column density for this molecule.

Fig. C.61. Detected SO lines towards N38. Based on results from the source sample we conclude that the detected lines are optically thick, and since no isotopologues were detected we were not able to derive a column density for this molecule.

Fig. C.62. Detected H₂CS lines towards N38. The values obtained from model fitting (model in blue) overlapped on the observed spectrum (in black) for this molecule were column density of $1.0 (0.5) \times 10^{15} \text{cm}^{-2}$, with excitation temperature 100 (50)K.

Fig. C.63. Detected CH_3OH lines towards N48. Based on results from the source sample we conclude that the detected lines are optically thick, and since no isotopologues were detected we were not able to derive a column density for this molecule.

Fig. C.64. Detected SO lines towards N48. Based on results from the source sample we conclude that the detected lines are optically thick, and since no isotopologues were detected we were not able to derive a column density for this molecule.

Fig. C.65. Detected SO lines towards S8. Based on results from the source sample we conclude that the detected lines are optically thick, and since no isotopologues were detected we were not able to derive a column density for this molecule.

Appendix D: Molecule lists in spectra

This appendix presents tables with detected molecular lines for the source sample.

Table D.1. Detected molecular transitions towards S26. The listed line transitions are from best fit line models obtained using the software package CASSIS, on the spectrum taken at the position of peak continuum emission. The model parameters are listed in Table B.1. Only transitions above 6 K are listed ($\sim 3\sigma$), corresponding to about 0.6 Jy beam⁻¹.

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4}[\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
329.330552	C ¹⁸ O	(3 – 2)	31.61	0.02	–
329.385477	SO	(2 ₁ – 1 ₀)	15.81	0.14	0.04
329.573452	HNCO	(15 _{2,14} – 14 _{2,13})	296.83	4.72	0.23
329.584800	HNCO	(15 _{2,13} – 14 _{2,12})	296.83	4.72	0.23
329.628168	CH ₃ OH	(24 _{7,18,3} – 24 _{4,21,6})	1323.36	0.00	0.00
329.632881	CH ₃ OH	(12 _{2,10,0} – 11 _{3,9,0})	218.80	0.60	8.25
329.664367	HNCO	(15 _{0,15} – 14 _{0,14})	126.58	5.04	0.99
330.001752	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,0} – 6 _{0,6,0})	76.50	1.58	0.19
330.191103	³⁴ SO ₂	(8 _{2,6} – 7 _{1,7})	42.77	1.19	0.22
330.194042	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{-1,7,0} – 6 _{-1,6,0})	69.01	1.55	0.21
330.252798	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,+0} – 6 _{0,6,+0})	63.41	1.58	0.22
330.342534	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,3,+0} – 6 _{4,2,+0})	144.21	1.07	0.07
330.342534	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,4,-0} – 6 _{4,3,-0})	144.21	1.07	0.07
330.349987	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,6,-0} – 6 _{2,5,-0})	101.23	1.46	0.14
330.355512	CH ₃ OH	(20 _{3,17,0} – 19 _{4,16,0})	537.04	0.64	0.60
330.371293	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,+0} – 6 _{3,4,+0})	113.47	1.29	0.11
330.373443	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,4,-0} – 6 _{3,3,-0})	113.47	1.29	0.11
330.405456	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(16 _{2,15,3} – 15 _{1,14,3})	128.46	1.65	0.02
330.405456	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(16 _{2,15,5} – 15 _{1,14,5})	128.46	1.65	0.03
330.406503	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(16 _{2,15,1} – 15 _{1,14,1})	128.46	1.65	0.07
330.407010	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(49 _{10,40,3} – 48 _{11,37,3})	1256.39	0.20	0.00
330.407549	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(16 _{2,15,0} – 15 _{1,14,0})	128.46	1.65	0.04
330.442421	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,6,0} – 6 _{1,5,0})	84.49	1.59	0.18
330.463873	CH ₃ OH	(11 _{1,10,-0} – 11 _{0,11,+0})	165.27	3.90	0.30
330.464947	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,+0} – 6 _{2,4,+0})	101.24	1.46	0.14
330.535222	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,0} – 6 _{2,4,0})	85.80	1.44	0.16
330.535890	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{-2,6,0} – 6 _{-2,5,0})	89.45	1.46	0.16
330.557569	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{-9,0} – 17 _{9,0})	728.67	23.60	0.03
330.557569	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{9,0} – 17 _{-9,0})	728.67	23.60	0.03
330.587965	¹³ CO	(3 – 2)	31.73	0.02	–
330.665207	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{8,0} – 17 _{8,0})	607.57	25.30	0.05
330.667565	³⁴ SO ₂	(21 _{2,20} – 21 _{1,21})	218.58	1.45	0.16
330.760284	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{7,0} – 17 _{7,0})	500.65	26.80	0.08
330.793887	CH ₃ OH	(8 _{3,5,2} – 9 _{2,7,2})	146.28	0.54	10.28
330.842762	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{-6,0} – 17 _{6,0})	407.94	28.00	0.13
330.842762	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{6,0} – 17 _{-6,0})	407.94	28.00	0.13
330.848569	HNCO	(15 _{1,14} – 14 _{1,13})	170.31	5.01	0.68
330.912608	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{5,0} – 17 _{5,0})	329.46	29.10	0.18
330.969794	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{4,0} – 17 _{4,0})	265.22	30.00	0.25
331.014296	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{-3,0} – 17 _{3,0})	215.24	30.70	0.31
331.014296	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{3,0} – 17 _{-3,0})	215.24	30.70	0.31
331.046096	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{2,0} – 17 _{2,0})	179.53	31.20	0.37
331.065182	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{1,0} – 17 _{1,0})	158.11	31.50	0.40
331.071544	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{0,0} – 17 _{0,0})	150.96	31.60	0.42
331.220371	CH ₃ OH	(16 _{1,16,2} – 15 _{2,13,2})	320.63	0.52	3.38
331.502319	CH ₃ OH	(11 _{1,10,0} – 11 _{0,11,0})	169.01	3.93	80.45
331.580244	SO ₂	(11 _{6,6} – 12 _{5,7})	148.95	0.43	1.11
331.748518	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(18 _{-1,3} – 17 _{1,3})	670.28	31.40	0.08
331.992354	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(18 _{-2,2} – 17 _{2,2})	731.74	31.20	0.05
331.992354	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(18 _{2,2} – 17 _{-2,2})	731.74	31.20	0.05
332.015818	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(18 _{0,2} – 17 _{0,2})	676.58	31.60	0.08
332.017856	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(18 _{1,2} – 17 _{1,2})	697.02	31.50	0.07
332.028758	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(18 _{-4,3} – 17 _{4,3})	737.59	30.00	0.05
332.028758	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(18 _{4,3} – 17 _{-4,3})	737.59	30.00	0.05
332.091431	SO ₂	(21 _{2,20} – 21 _{1,21})	219.53	1.51	3.99
332.129700	OC ³⁴ S	(28 – 27)	231.16	1.07	0.13
332.173573	³⁴ SO ₂	(23 _{3,21} – 23 _{2,22})	274.74	2.54	0.19

Table D.1. continued.

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4}[\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
332.387753	CH ₃ CN, $v_8=1$	(18 _{1,3} – 17 _{-1,3})	670.57	31.60	0.08
332.505242	SO ₂	(4 _{3,1} – 3 _{2,2})	31.29	3.29	8.73
332.570617	CH ₃ OCHO	(30 _{1,29,2} – 29 _{2,28,1})	256.98	0.80	0.01
332.570888	CH ₃ OCHO	(30 _{2,29,1} – 29 _{2,28,1})	256.98	5.53	0.07
332.571107	CH ₃ OCHO	(30 _{1,29,2} – 29 _{1,28,2})	256.98	5.53	0.07
332.571378	CH ₃ OCHO	(30 _{2,29,1} – 29 _{1,28,2})	256.98	0.80	0.01
332.575715	CH ₃ OCHO	(30 _{1,29,0} – 29 _{2,28,0})	256.96	0.80	0.01
332.575985	CH ₃ OCHO	(30 _{2,29,0} – 29 _{2,28,0})	256.96	5.53	0.07
332.576202	CH ₃ OCHO	(30 _{1,29,0} – 29 _{1,28,0})	256.96	5.53	0.07
332.576472	CH ₃ OCHO	(30 _{2,29,0} – 29 _{1,28,0})	256.96	0.80	0.01
332.836225	³⁴ SO ₂	(16 _{4,12} – 16 _{3,13})	162.90	3.02	0.39
332.996563	CH ₃ OH	(22 _{2,20,2} – 21 _{3,18,2})	614.49	0.63	0.29
333.114779	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,6,-0} – 6 _{1,5,-0})	78.52	1.59	0.19
333.448974	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{0,31,2} – 30 _{1,30,1})	259.59	0.82	0.01
333.448976	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{1,31,1} – 30 _{1,30,1})	259.59	5.73	0.08
333.448977	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{0,31,2} – 30 _{0,30,2})	259.59	5.73	0.08
333.448979	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{1,31,1} – 30 _{0,30,2})	259.59	0.82	0.01
333.449417	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{0,31,0} – 30 _{1,30,0})	259.57	0.91	0.01
333.449419	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{1,31,0} – 30 _{1,30,0})	259.57	5.64	0.08
333.449421	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{0,31,0} – 30 _{0,30,0})	259.57	5.64	0.08
333.449422	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{1,31,0} – 30 _{0,30,0})	259.57	0.91	0.01
333.449750	CH ₃ OCHO	(40 _{13,27,5} – 40 _{12,28,5})	782.89	0.53	0.00
333.864722	CH ₃ OH	(9 _{1,8,1} – 8 _{2,6,2})	125.52	0.01	0.21
333.900983	³⁴ SO	(8 ₇ – 7 ₆)	79.86	4.69	1.92
334.426571	CH ₃ OH	(3 _{0,3,4} – 2 _{1,2,4})	314.47	0.56	0.79
334.673353	SO ₂	(8 _{2,6} – 7 _{1,7})	43.15	1.27	5.69
335.133570	CH ₃ OH	(2 _{2,1,0} – 3 _{1,2,0})	44.67	0.27	4.07
335.395500	HDO	(3 _{3,1} – 4 _{2,2})	335.27	0.26	0.09
335.560207	CH ₃ OH	(12 _{1,11,-0} – 12 _{0,12,+0})	192.66	4.04	0.25
335.582017	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,7,0} – 6 _{1,6,0})	78.97	1.63	52.22
336.089228	SO ₂	(23 _{3,21} – 23 _{2,22})	276.02	2.67	4.71
336.438224	CH ₃ OH	(14 _{7,7,0} – 15 _{6,9,0})	488.22	0.36	0.37
336.438224	CH ₃ OH	(14 _{7,8,0} – 15 _{6,10,0})	488.22	0.36	0.37
336.520084	HC ₃ N	(37 – 36)	306.91	30.50	0.46
336.553811	SO	(11 ₁₀ – 10 ₁₀)	142.88	0.06	0.04
336.669581	SO ₂	(16 _{7,9} – 17 _{6,12})	245.12	0.58	0.93
336.865149	CH ₃ OH	(12 _{1,11,0} – 12 _{0,12,0})	197.07	4.07	66.37
337.060513	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{1,5} – 2 _{2,5})	32.35	0.00	0.00
337.060709	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{0,5} – 2 _{1,5})	32.35	0.01	0.00
337.060831	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{2,5} – 2 _{3,5})	32.35	0.00	0.00
337.060936	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{2,5} – 2 _{2,5})	32.35	0.01	0.03
337.060988	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{4,5} – 2 _{3,5})	32.35	0.02	0.08
337.060988	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{5,5} – 2 _{4,5})	32.35	0.02	0.12
337.061050	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{1,5} – 2 _{1,5})	32.35	0.01	0.02
337.061123	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{3,5} – 2 _{3,5})	32.35	0.01	0.03
337.061214	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{0,5} – 2 _{0,5})	32.35	0.02	0.02
337.061226	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{3,5} – 2 _{2,5})	32.35	0.01	0.05
337.061471	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{2,5} – 2 _{1,5})	32.35	0.01	0.03
337.061553	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{1,5} – 2 _{0,5})	32.35	0.01	0.01
337.061951	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{4,5} – 2 _{4,5})	32.35	0.00	0.02
337.062093	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{3,5} – 2 _{4,5})	32.35	0.00	0.00
337.135853	CH ₃ OH	(3 _{3,1,1} – 4 _{2,3,1})	61.64	0.16	2.79
337.197845	³³ SO	(8 _{7,7,5} – 7 _{6,6,5})	80.53	4.70	0.06
337.198022	³³ SO	(8 _{7,6,5} – 7 _{6,5,5})	80.53	4.62	0.05
337.198620	³³ SO	(8 _{7,8,5} – 7 _{6,7,5})	80.53	4.83	0.07
337.199371	³³ SO	(8 _{7,5,5} – 7 _{6,4,5})	80.54	4.65	0.05
337.252172	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,6} – 6 _{3,4,6})	722.84	1.39	0.07
337.252173	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,4,6} – 6 _{3,3,6})	722.84	1.39	0.07
337.273561	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,3,6} – 6 _{4,2,6})	679.25	1.13	0.09

Table D.1. continued.

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4}[\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
337.273561	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,4,6} – 6 _{4,3,6})	679.25	1.13	0.09
337.284320	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,6} – 6 _{0,6,6})	572.96	1.68	0.38
337.295913	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,7} – 6 _{3,4,7})	686.20	1.37	0.10
337.297484	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,7,3} – 6 _{1,6,3})	390.02	1.65	2.35
337.302644	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,6,7} – 6 _{2,5,7})	650.99	1.55	0.16
337.312360	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,7,8} – 6 _{1,6,8})	596.79	1.65	0.30
337.396459	C ³⁴ S	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	64.77	8.00	1.21
337.463703	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{6,1,3} – 6 _{6,0,3})	533.02	0.45	0.15
337.463703	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{6,2,3} – 6 _{6,1,3})	533.02	0.45	0.15
337.519138	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,4,4} – 6 _{3,3,4})	482.23	1.38	0.78
337.546116	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,2,3} – 6 _{5,1,3})	485.37	0.82	0.45
337.546116	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,3,3} – 6 _{5,2,3})	485.37	0.82	0.45
337.580147	³⁴ SO	(8 ₈ – 7 ₇)	86.07	4.89	2.11
337.581680	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,4,4} – 6 _{4,3,4})	428.20	1.13	1.09
337.590319	t-HCOOH	(15 _{6,10} – 14 _{6,9})	243.95	3.68	0.03
337.590319	t-HCOOH	(15 _{6,9} – 14 _{6,8})	243.95	3.68	0.03
337.605288	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,6,5} – 6 _{2,5,5})	429.43	1.56	1.49
337.610661	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,5} – 6 _{3,4,5})	387.45	1.37	2.00
337.610680	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{6,1,4} – 6 _{6,0,4})	657.12	0.43	0.04
337.625753	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,6,3} – 6 _{2,5,3})	363.50	1.55	2.85
337.635754	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,3} – 6 _{2,4,3})	363.50	1.55	2.85
337.642478	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,7,4} – 6 _{1,6,4})	356.30	1.65	3.28
337.643915	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,4} – 6 _{0,6,4})	365.40	1.69	3.06
337.646042	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,3,5} – 6 _{4,2,5})	470.22	1.14	0.72
337.648209	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,2,5} – 6 _{5,1,5})	610.96	0.83	0.13
337.655199	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,3} – 6 _{3,4,3})	460.94	1.38	0.96
337.655236	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,4,3} – 6 _{3,3,3})	460.94	1.38	0.96
337.671238	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,4} – 6 _{2,4,4})	464.72	1.55	1.04
337.685248	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,3,4} – 6 _{5,2,4})	493.95	0.83	0.41
337.685614	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,3,3} – 6 _{4,2,3})	545.90	1.15	0.34
337.685614	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,4,3} – 6 _{4,3,3})	545.90	1.15	0.34
337.707568	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,6,5} – 6 _{1,5,5})	478.21	1.65	0.97
337.748830	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,3} – 6 _{0,6,3})	488.49	1.69	0.89
337.837801	CH ₃ OH	(20 _{6,14,2} – 21 _{5,17,2})	675.95	0.60	0.13
337.969438	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,6,3} – 6 _{1,5,3})	390.15	1.66	2.35
338.083195	H ₂ CS	(10 _{1,10} – 9 _{1,9})	102.43	5.77	0.22
338.124488	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,1} – 6 _{0,6,1})	78.08	1.70	54.13
338.305993	SO ₂	(18 _{4,14} – 18 _{3,15})	196.80	3.27	8.67
338.320356	³⁴ SO ₂	(13 _{2,12} – 12 _{1,11})	92.45	2.27	0.42
338.344588	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,7,2} – 6 _{1,6,2})	70.55	1.67	57.29
338.404610	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{6,2,1} – 6 _{6,1,1})	243.79	0.45	2.75
338.408698	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,0} – 6 _{0,6,0})	64.98	1.70	61.82
338.430975	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{6,1,2} – 6 _{6,0,2})	253.95	0.45	2.49
338.442367	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{6,1,0} – 6 _{6,0,0})	258.70	0.45	2.37
338.442367	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{6,2,0} – 6 _{6,1,0})	258.70	0.45	2.37
338.456536	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,3,2} – 6 _{5,2,2})	189.00	0.83	8.77
338.475226	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,2,1} – 6 _{5,1,1})	201.06	0.83	7.78
338.486322	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,2,0} – 6 _{5,1,0})	202.88	0.84	7.67
338.486322	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,3,0} – 6 _{5,2,0})	202.88	0.84	7.67
338.504065	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,4,2} – 6 _{4,3,2})	152.89	1.15	17.29
338.512632	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,4,0} – 6 _{4,3,0})	145.33	1.15	18.68
338.512644	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,3,0} – 6 _{4,2,0})	145.33	1.15	18.68
338.512853	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,6,0} – 6 _{2,5,0})	102.70	1.57	39.20
338.530257	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,3,1} – 6 _{4,2,1})	160.99	1.15	16.04
338.540826	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,0} – 6 _{3,4,0})	114.79	1.39	30.64
338.543152	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,4,0} – 6 _{3,3,0})	114.79	1.39	30.64
338.559963	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,4,2} – 6 _{3,3,2})	127.71	1.40	27.12
338.583216	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,1} – 6 _{3,4,1})	112.71	1.39	31.38
338.611810	SO ₂	(20 _{1,19} – 19 _{2,18})	198.88	2.87	8.28
338.614936	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,6,1} – 6 _{1,5,1})	86.05	1.71	50.30

Table D.1. continued.

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4}[\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
338.639802	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,0} – 6 _{2,4,0})	102.72	1.58	39.21
338.721693	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,6,1} – 6 _{2,5,1})	87.26	1.55	45.00
338.722898	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,2} – 6 _{2,4,2})	90.91	1.57	43.90
338.759948	CH ₃ OH	(13 _{0,13,+0} – 12 _{1,12,+0})	205.95	2.18	0.13
338.785687	³⁴ SO ₂	(14 _{4,10} – 14 _{3,11})	134.34	3.08	0.43
339.341459	SO	(3 ₃ – 2 ₃)	25.51	0.14	0.08
339.491473	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{1,18,0} – 18 _{2,17,0})	176.10	2.03	0.04
339.491529	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{1,18,1} – 18 _{2,17,1})	176.10	2.03	0.06
339.491586	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{1,18,3} – 18 _{2,17,3})	176.10	2.03	0.02
339.491586	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{1,18,5} – 18 _{2,17,5})	176.10	2.03	0.02
339.857269	³⁴ SO	(8 ₉ – 7 ₈)	77.34	5.08	2.60
340.052575	C ³³ S	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	65.28	8.19	0.25
340.141143	CH ₃ OH	(2 _{2,0,0} – 3 _{1,3,0})	44.67	0.28	4.08
340.316406	SO ₂	(28 _{2,26} – 28 _{1,27})	391.80	2.58	2.05
340.393659	CH ₃ OH	(16 _{6,11,0} – 17 _{5,12,0})	509.17	0.50	0.46
340.393745	CH ₃ OH	(16 _{6,10,0} – 17 _{5,13,0})	509.17	0.50	0.46
340.449273	OCS	(28 – 27)	236.95	1.15	1.22
340.683969	CH ₃ OH	(11 _{1,11,4} – 10 _{0,10,4})	444.25	1.10	1.36
340.714155	SO	(8 ₇ – 7 ₆)	81.25	4.99	3.79
340.837357	³³ SO	(8 _{8,6,5} – 7 _{7,5,5})	86.75	4.89	0.05
340.837862	³³ SO	(8 _{8,7,5} – 7 _{7,6,5})	86.75	4.87	0.06
340.838679	³³ SO	(8 _{8,8,5} – 7 _{7,7,5})	86.75	4.92	0.07
340.839639	³³ SO	(8 _{8,9,5} – 7 _{7,8,5})	86.75	5.03	0.08
340.841735	³³ SO	(8 _{8,8,5} – 7 _{7,8,5})	86.75	0.11	0.00
341.131665	CH ₃ OH	(13 _{1,12,-0} – 13 _{0,13,+0})	222.32	4.19	0.20
341.275524	SO ₂	(21 _{8,14} – 22 _{7,15})	369.13	0.69	0.49
341.403068	SO ₂	(40 _{4,36} – 40 _{3,37})	808.37	4.11	0.14
341.415615	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,6,0} – 6 _{1,5,0})	80.09	1.71	52.63
341.673961	SO ₂	(36 _{5,31} – 36 _{4,32})	678.52	4.34	0.40
342.208857	³⁴ SO ₂	(5 _{3,3} – 4 _{2,2})	35.10	3.10	0.37
342.231633	³⁴ SO ₂	(20 _{1,19} – 19 _{2,18})	198.24	3.06	0.35
342.332013	³⁴ SO ₂	(12 _{4,8} – 12 _{3,9})	109.51	3.06	0.45
342.358225	CH ₃ OCHO	(30 _{2,28,2} – 29 _{2,27,2})	269.50	5.98	0.07
342.359508	CH ₃ OCHO	(30 _{3,28,0} – 29 _{3,27,0})	269.49	5.98	0.07
342.360148	CH ₃ OCHO	(57 _{11,47,1} – 57 _{10,48,1})	1069.40	0.56	0.00
342.521194	t-HCOOH	(16 _{1,16} – 15 _{1,15})	143.59	4.56	0.06
342.607898	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{0,19,3} – 18 _{1,18,3})	167.14	3.30	0.03
342.607898	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{0,19,5} – 18 _{1,18,5})	167.14	3.30	0.04
342.607971	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{0,19,1} – 18 _{1,18,1})	167.14	3.30	0.11
342.608044	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{0,19,0} – 18 _{1,18,0})	167.14	3.30	0.07
342.726474	CH ₃ OH	(20 _{6,15,5} – 19 _{7,13,5})	978.98	0.68	0.01
342.729796	CH ₃ OH	(13 _{1,12,0} – 13 _{0,13,0})	227.47	4.23	53.17
342.761625	SO ₂	(34 _{3,31} – 34 _{2,32})	581.92	3.45	0.67
342.882850	CS	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	65.83	8.40	–
343.086102	³³ SO	(8 _{9,7,5} – 7 _{8,6,5})	78.03	5.11	0.07
343.087298	³³ SO	(8 _{9,8,5} – 7 _{8,7,5})	78.03	5.09	0.08
343.088078	³³ SO	(8 _{9,9,5} – 7 _{8,8,5})	78.03	5.13	0.09
343.088295	³³ SO	(8 _{9,10,5} – 7 _{8,9,5})	78.04	5.23	0.10
343.147898	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{1,30,2} – 30 _{2,29,1})	273.44	0.89	0.01
343.148047	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{2,30,1} – 30 _{2,29,1})	273.44	6.08	0.07
343.148169	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{1,30,2} – 30 _{1,29,2})	273.44	6.08	0.07
343.148318	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{2,30,1} – 30 _{1,29,2})	273.44	0.89	0.01
343.149303	CH ₃ OCHO	(17 _{5,12,0} – 16 _{4,13,0})	107.81	0.25	0.01
343.152958	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{1,30,0} – 30 _{2,29,0})	273.43	0.89	0.01
343.153106	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{2,30,0} – 30 _{2,29,0})	273.43	6.08	0.07
343.153227	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{1,30,0} – 30 _{1,29,0})	273.43	6.08	0.07
343.153376	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{2,30,0} – 30 _{1,29,0})	273.43	0.89	0.01
343.153762	CH ₃ OCHO	(26 _{13,13,0} – 26 _{12,14,0})	319.30	0.46	0.00
343.153770	CH ₃ OCHO	(26 _{13,14,0} – 26 _{12,15,0})	319.30	0.46	0.00

Table D.1. continued.

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4}[\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
343.325713	H ₂ ¹³ CO	(5 _{1,5} – 4 _{1,4})	61.28	11.20	0.06
343.409963	H ₂ CS	(10 _{3,8} – 9 _{3,7})	209.10	5.56	0.09
343.414146	H ₂ CS	(10 _{3,7} – 9 _{3,6})	209.10	5.56	0.09
343.753320	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(17 _{2,16,3} – 16 _{1,15,3})	143.70	1.96	0.02
343.753320	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(17 _{2,16,5} – 16 _{1,15,5})	143.70	1.96	0.01
343.754216	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(17 _{2,16,1} – 16 _{1,15,1})	143.70	1.96	0.07
343.952343	t-HCOOH	(15 _{1,14} – 14 _{1,13})	136.28	4.60	0.06
343.983268	OC ³⁴ S	(29 – 28)	247.67	1.19	0.12
344.029259	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{0,32,2} – 31 _{1,31,1})	276.10	0.77	0.01
344.029260	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{1,32,1} – 31 _{1,31,1})	276.10	6.43	0.07
344.029261	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{0,32,2} – 31 _{0,31,2})	276.10	6.43	0.07
344.029262	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{1,32,1} – 31 _{0,31,2})	276.10	0.77	0.01
344.029644	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{0,32,0} – 31 _{1,31,0})	276.08	1.00	0.01
344.029645	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{1,32,0} – 31 _{1,31,0})	276.08	6.20	0.07
344.029646	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{0,32,0} – 31 _{0,31,0})	276.08	6.20	0.07
344.029647	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{1,32,0} – 31 _{0,31,0})	276.08	1.00	0.01
344.109039	CH ₃ OH	(18 _{2,17,1} – 17 _{3,15,1})	419.40	0.68	1.71
344.200109	HC ¹⁵ N	(4 – 3)	41.30	18.80	3.51
344.245346	³⁴ SO ₂	(10 _{4,6} – 10 _{3,7})	88.38	2.96	0.43
344.310612	SO	(8 ₈ – 7 ₇)	87.48	5.19	4.15
344.312267	CH ₃ OH	(10 _{2,9,5} – 11 _{3,9,5})	491.91	1.77	1.22
344.357816	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{1,19,3} – 18 _{0,18,3})	167.18	3.36	0.03
344.357816	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{1,19,5} – 18 _{0,18,5})	167.18	3.36	0.01
344.357826	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(38 _{4,35,3} – 38 _{3,36,3})	697.07	1.59	0.00
344.357826	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(38 _{4,35,5} – 38 _{3,36,5})	697.07	1.59	0.00
344.357929	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{1,19,1} – 18 _{0,18,1})	167.18	3.36	0.11
344.358041	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{1,19,0} – 18 _{0,18,0})	167.18	3.36	0.04
344.358087	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(38 _{4,35,1} – 38 _{3,36,1})	697.07	1.59	0.00
344.358347	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(38 _{4,35,0} – 38 _{3,36,0})	697.07	1.59	0.00
344.443433	CH ₃ OH	(19 _{1,19,0} – 18 _{2,16,0})	451.23	0.73	1.40
344.581045	³⁴ SO ₂	(19 _{1,19} – 18 _{0,18})	167.41	5.16	0.72
344.807915	³⁴ SO ₂	(13 _{4,10} – 13 _{3,11})	121.46	3.17	0.45
344.987585	³⁴ SO ₂	(15 _{4,12} – 15 _{3,13})	148.13	3.27	0.42
344.998160	³⁴ SO ₂	(11 _{4,8} – 11 _{3,9})	98.48	3.05	0.44
345.030561	t-HCOOH	(16 _{0,16} – 15 _{0,15})	143.05	4.66	0.06
345.148971	SO ₂	(5 _{5,1} – 6 _{4,2})	75.14	0.10	0.21
345.168664	³⁴ SO ₂	(8 _{4,4} – 8 _{3,5})	70.94	2.75	0.37
345.285620	³⁴ SO ₂	(9 _{4,6} – 9 _{3,7})	79.20	2.88	0.40
345.338538	SO ₂	(13 _{2,12} – 12 _{1,11})	92.98	2.38	10.53
345.448984	SO ₂	(26 _{9,17} – 27 _{8,20})	521.00	0.76	0.19
345.519656	³⁴ SO ₂	(7 _{4,4} – 7 _{3,5})	63.61	2.59	0.33
345.553093	³⁴ SO ₂	(6 _{4,2} – 6 _{3,3})	57.19	2.35	0.27
345.609010	HC ₃ N	(38 – 37)	323.49	33.00	0.43
345.651293	³⁴ SO ₂	(5 _{4,2} – 5 _{3,3})	51.69	1.96	0.20
345.678787	³⁴ SO ₂	(4 _{4,0} – 4 _{3,1})	47.10	1.31	0.11
345.795990	CO	(3 – 2)	33.19	0.03	–
345.903916	CH ₃ OH	(16 _{1,15,0} – 15 _{2,14,0})	332.65	1.04	5.49
345.919260	CH ₃ OH	(18 _{3,15,2} – 17 _{4,14,2})	459.43	0.73	1.21
345.929349	³⁴ SO ₂	(17 _{4,14} – 17 _{3,15})	178.51	3.37	0.38
346.202719	CH ₃ OH	(5 _{4,2,0} – 6 _{3,3,0})	115.16	0.22	3.36
346.204271	CH ₃ OH	(5 _{4,1,0} – 6 _{3,4,0})	115.16	0.22	3.36
346.523878	SO ₂	(16 _{4,12} – 16 _{3,13})	164.47	3.39	10.03
346.528481	SO	(8 ₉ – 7 ₈)	78.78	5.38	5.11
346.652169	SO ₂	(19 _{1,19} – 18 _{0,18})	168.14	5.22	17.70
346.718858	t-HCOOH	(15 _{2,13} – 14 _{2,12})	144.46	4.66	0.06
347.188283	CH ₃ OH	(14 _{1,13,-0} – 14 _{0,14,+0})	254.25	4.36	0.16
347.330581	SiO	(8 ₀ – 7 ₀)	75.02	22.00	0.34
348.117469	³⁴ SO ₂	(19 _{4,16} – 19 _{3,17})	212.61	3.50	0.33
348.387800	SO ₂	(24 _{2,22} – 23 _{3,21})	292.74	1.91	2.85

Table D.1. continued.

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4}[\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
348.534365	H ₂ CS	(10 _{1,9} – 9 _{1,8})	105.19	6.32	0.22
348.911401	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{-9,0} – 18 _{9,0})	745.42	28.70	0.03
348.911401	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{9,0} – 18 _{-9,0})	745.42	28.70	0.03
349.024971	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{8,0} – 18 _{8,0})	624.32	30.50	0.05
349.106997	CH ₃ OH	(14 _{1,13,0} – 14 _{0,14,0})	260.20	4.41	41.38
349.125287	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{7,0} – 18 _{7,0})	517.41	32.10	0.09
349.212311	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{-6,0} – 18 _{6,0})	424.70	33.40	0.13
349.212311	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{6,0} – 18 _{-6,0})	424.70	33.40	0.13
349.286006	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{5,0} – 18 _{5,0})	346.22	34.60	0.19
349.346343	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{4,0} – 18 _{4,0})	281.99	35.50	0.26
349.393297	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{-3,0} – 18 _{3,0})	232.01	36.30	0.32
349.393297	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{3,0} – 18 _{-3,0})	232.01	36.30	0.32
349.426850	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{2,0} – 18 _{2,0})	196.30	36.80	0.38
349.446987	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{1,0} – 18 _{1,0})	174.88	37.10	0.42
349.453700	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{0,0} – 18 _{0,0})	167.74	37.20	0.43
350.103118	CH ₃ OH	(1 _{1,1,+0} – 0 _{0,0,+0})	16.80	3.29	0.13
350.168100	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(19 _{1,3} – 18 _{-1,3})	687.09	37.00	0.08
350.286493	CH ₃ OH	(15 _{3,12,4} – 16 _{4,13,4})	694.83	2.09	0.27
350.333059	HNCO	(16 _{1,16} – 15 _{1,15})	186.20	5.97	0.68
350.423619	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(19 _{-2,2} – 18 _{2,2})	748.55	36.80	0.05
350.423619	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(19 _{2,2} – 18 _{-2,2})	748.55	36.80	0.05
350.444906	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(19 _{0,2} – 18 _{0,2})	693.40	37.20	0.08
350.449631	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(19 _{1,2} – 18 _{1,2})	713.84	37.10	0.07
350.465645	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(19 _{-4,3} – 18 _{4,3})	754.41	35.60	0.05
350.465645	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(19 _{4,3} – 18 _{-4,3})	754.41	35.60	0.05
350.687662	CH ₃ OH	(4 _{0,4,1} – 3 _{1,3,2})	36.34	0.87	23.51
350.842670	CH ₃ CN, v ₈ =1	(19 _{-1,3} – 18 _{1,3})	687.41	37.20	0.08
350.862756	SO ₂	(10 _{6,4} – 11 _{5,7})	138.84	0.44	1.00
350.905100	CH ₃ OH	(1 _{1,1,0} – 0 _{0,0,0})	16.84	3.32	36.36
351.236479	CH ₃ OH	(9 _{5,4,1} – 10 _{4,6,1})	240.51	0.36	2.70
351.257223	SO ₂	(5 _{3,3} – 4 _{2,2})	35.89	3.36	9.42
351.537795	HNCO	(16 _{2,15} – 15 _{2,14})	313.70	5.75	0.22
351.551573	HNCO	(16 _{2,14} – 15 _{2,13})	313.70	5.75	0.22
351.633257	HNCO	(16 _{0,16} – 15 _{0,15})	143.46	6.13	0.99
351.768645	H ₂ CO	(5 _{1,5} – 4 _{1,4})	62.45	12.00	–
351.873873	SO ₂	(14 _{4,10} – 14 _{3,11})	135.87	3.43	11.00
351.994870	HNCO	(23 _{1,23} – 24 _{0,24})	333.30	2.31	0.11
352.082921	³⁴ SO ₂	(21 _{4,18} – 21 _{3,19})	250.41	3.65	0.27
352.599570	OCS	(29 – 28)	253.88	1.28	1.11
352.897581	HNCO	(16 _{1,15} – 15 _{1,14})	187.25	6.10	0.68
353.723522	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{1,31,2} – 31 _{2,30,1})	290.42	0.97	0.01
353.728572	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{1,31,0} – 31 _{2,30,0})	290.41	0.98	0.01
353.739964	CH ₃ OH	(15 _{1,14,-0} – 15 _{0,15,+0})	288.46	4.54	0.12
354.127629	CH ₃ OH	(19 _{2,17,3} – 18 _{1,17,3})	738.20	1.43	0.15
354.445952	CH ₃ OH	(4 _{1,3,0} – 3 _{0,3,0})	43.71	1.27	0.11
354.505477	HCN	(4 – 3)	42.53	20.50	–
354.604757	CH ₃ OCHO	(29 _{15,14,3} – 28 _{15,13,3})	592.88	4.99	0.00
354.604757	CH ₃ OCHO	(29 _{15,15,3} – 28 _{15,14,3})	592.88	4.99	0.00
354.607764	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{0,33,2} – 32 _{1,32,1})	293.12	0.70	0.01
354.607764	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{1,33,1} – 32 _{1,32,1})	293.12	7.19	0.06
354.607765	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{0,33,2} – 32 _{0,32,2})	293.12	7.19	0.06
354.607765	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{1,33,1} – 32 _{0,32,2})	293.12	0.70	0.01
354.608091	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{0,33,0} – 32 _{1,32,0})	293.10	1.10	0.01
354.608092	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{0,33,0} – 32 _{0,32,0})	293.10	6.79	0.06
354.608092	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{1,33,0} – 32 _{1,32,0})	293.10	6.79	0.06
354.608093	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{1,33,0} – 32 _{0,32,0})	293.10	1.10	0.01
354.697463	HC ₃ N	(39 – 38)	340.52	35.70	0.40
355.045517	SO ₂	(12 _{4,8} – 12 _{3,9})	111.00	3.40	11.34
355.602945	CH ₃ OH	(13 _{0,13,0} – 12 _{1,12,0})	211.03	2.53	34.95
356.007235	CH ₃ OH	(15 _{1,14,0} – 15 _{0,15,0})	295.26	4.60	31.32

Table D.1. continued.

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4}[\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
356.040644	SO ₂	(15 _{7,9} – 16 _{6,10})	230.41	0.64	0.98
356.137265	t-HCOOH	(16 _{2,15} – 15 _{2,14})	158.67	5.07	0.06
356.222250	³⁴ SO ₂	(25 _{3,23} – 25 _{2,24})	319.52	2.97	0.14
356.734223	HCO ⁺	(4 – 3)	42.80	35.70	–
356.755190	SO ₂	(10 _{4,6} – 10 _{3,7})	89.83	3.28	10.88
357.102182	³⁴ SO ₂	(20 _{0,20} – 19 _{1,19})	184.55	5.81	0.69
357.165390	SO ₂	(13 _{4,10} – 13 _{3,11})	122.97	3.51	11.34
357.241193	SO ₂	(15 _{4,12} – 15 _{3,13})	149.68	3.62	10.73
357.387579	SO ₂	(11 _{4,8} – 11 _{3,9})	99.95	3.38	11.26
357.459408	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(18 _{2,17,3} – 17 _{1,16,3})	159.81	2.31	0.02
357.459408	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(18 _{2,17,5} – 17 _{1,16,5})	159.81	2.31	0.03
357.460164	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(18 _{2,17,1} – 17 _{1,16,1})	159.81	2.31	0.07
357.460920	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(18 _{2,17,0} – 17 _{1,16,0})	159.81	2.31	0.04
357.581449	SO ₂	(8 _{4,4} – 8 _{3,5})	72.36	3.06	9.45
357.657954	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,0} – 6 _{1,5,0})	85.80	1.63	0.16
357.671821	SO ₂	(9 _{4,6} – 9 _{3,7})	80.64	3.20	10.30
357.892442	SO ₂	(7 _{4,4} – 7 _{3,5})	65.01	2.87	8.32
357.925848	SO ₂	(6 _{4,2} – 6 _{3,3})	58.58	2.60	6.89
357.962905	SO ₂	(17 _{4,14} – 17 _{3,15})	180.11	3.73	9.64
358.013154	SO ₂	(5 _{4,2} – 5 _{3,3})	53.07	2.18	5.11
358.037887	SO ₂	(4 _{4,0} – 4 _{3,1})	48.48	1.45	2.89
358.215633	SO ₂	(20 _{0,20} – 19 _{1,19})	185.33	5.83	16.89
358.347316	³⁴ SO ₂	(23 _{4,20} – 23 _{3,21})	291.93	3.86	0.21
358.414648	CH ₃ OH	(10 _{6,5,1} – 11 _{5,6,1})	306.43	0.34	1.40
358.449468	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(5 _{5,1,5} – 4 _{4,0,5})	48.80	3.71	0.01
358.449478	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(5 _{5,0,5} – 4 _{4,1,5})	48.80	3.71	0.04
358.451541	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(5 _{5,0,3} – 4 _{4,0,3})	48.80	3.71	0.03
358.452015	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(5 _{5,0,1} – 4 _{4,0,1})	48.80	3.71	0.10
358.454082	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(5 _{5,1,1} – 4 _{4,1,1})	48.80	3.71	0.10
358.456618	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(5 _{5,1,0} – 4 _{4,0,0})	48.80	3.71	0.04
358.456629	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(5 _{5,0,0} – 4 _{4,1,0})	48.80	3.71	0.06
358.605799	CH ₃ OH	(4 _{1,3,1} – 3 _{0,3,1})	44.26	1.32	31.66
358.987971	³⁴ SO ₂	(15 _{2,14} – 14 _{1,13})	118.72	2.92	0.45
359.151158	SO ₂	(25 _{3,23} – 25 _{2,24})	320.93	3.10	3.60
359.651730	³⁴ SO ₂	(24 _{2,22} – 23 _{3,21})	292.00	2.20	0.12
359.770685	SO ₂	(19 _{4,16} – 19 _{3,17})	214.26	3.85	8.27
360.148273	t-HCOOH	(16 _{6,11} – 15 _{6,10})	261.23	4.58	0.03
360.148356	t-HCOOH	(16 _{6,10} – 15 _{6,9})	261.23	4.58	0.03
360.148518	t-HCOOH	(16 _{15,1} – 15 _{15,0})	858.50	0.64	0.00
360.148518	t-HCOOH	(16 _{15,2} – 15 _{15,1})	858.50	0.64	0.00
360.290404	SO ₂	(34 _{5,29} – 34 _{4,30})	611.96	4.80	0.66
360.584554	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(20 _{0,20,3} – 19 _{1,19,3})	184.48	3.89	0.03
360.584554	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(20 _{0,20,5} – 19 _{1,19,5})	184.48	3.89	0.01
360.584633	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(20 _{0,20,1} – 19 _{1,19,1})	184.48	3.89	0.10
360.584711	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(20 _{0,20,0} – 19 _{1,19,0})	184.48	3.89	0.04
360.661633	CH ₃ OH	(3 _{1,3,3} – 4 _{2,3,3})	339.14	2.64	2.56
360.721829	SO ₂	(20 _{8,12} – 21 _{7,15})	349.82	0.77	0.56
360.848946	CH ₃ OH	(11 _{0,11,1} – 10 _{1,9,1})	166.05	1.21	21.64

Table D.2. Detected molecular transitions towards N12. The listed line transitions are from best fit line models obtained using the software package CASSIS, on the spectrum taken at the position of peak continuum emission. The model parameters are listed in Table B.2. Only transitions above 6 K are listed ($\sim 3\sigma$), corresponding to about 0.6 Jy beam⁻¹.

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4}[\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
329.330552	C ¹⁸ O	(3 – 2)	31.61	0.02	7.27
330.463873	¹³ CH ₃ OH	(11 _{1,10,-0} – 11 _{0,11,+0})	165.27	3.90	0.09
330.464947	¹³ CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,+0} – 6 _{2,4,+0})	101.24	1.46	0.03
330.587965	¹³ CO	(3 – 2)	31.73	0.02	–
330.842762	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{-6,0} – 17 _{6,0})	407.94	28.00	0.04
330.842762	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{6,0} – 17 _{-6,0})	407.94	28.00	0.04
330.912608	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{5,0} – 17 _{5,0})	329.46	29.10	0.05
330.969794	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{4,0} – 17 _{4,0})	265.22	30.00	0.07
331.014296	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{-3,0} – 17 _{3,0})	215.24	30.70	0.09
331.014296	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{3,0} – 17 _{-3,0})	215.24	30.70	0.09
331.046096	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{2,0} – 17 _{2,0})	179.53	31.20	0.10
331.065182	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{1,0} – 17 _{1,0})	158.11	31.50	0.11
331.071544	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{0,0} – 17 _{0,0})	150.96	31.60	0.11
331.502319	CH ₃ OH	(11 _{1,10,0} – 11 _{0,11,0})	169.01	3.93	0.77
335.395500	HDO	(3 _{3,1} – 4 _{2,2})	335.27	0.26	0.05
335.560207	¹³ CH ₃ OH	(12 _{1,11,-0} – 12 _{0,12,+0})	192.66	4.04	0.08
335.582017	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,7,0} – 6 _{1,6,0})	78.97	1.63	0.50
336.865149	CH ₃ OH	(12 _{1,11,0} – 12 _{0,12,0})	197.07	4.07	0.63
337.396459	C ³⁴ S	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	64.77	8.00	2.42
338.083195	H ₂ CS	(10 _{1,10} – 9 _{1,9})	102.43	5.77	0.26
338.124488	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,1} – 6 _{0,6,1})	78.08	1.70	0.52
338.305993	SO ₂	(18 _{4,14} – 18 _{3,15})	196.80	3.27	0.07
338.344588	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,7,2} – 6 _{1,6,2})	70.55	1.67	0.55
338.408698	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,0} – 6 _{0,6,0})	64.98	1.70	0.59
338.486322	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,2,0} – 6 _{5,1,0})	202.88	0.84	0.07
338.486322	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,3,0} – 6 _{5,2,0})	202.88	0.84	0.07
338.504065	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,4,2} – 6 _{4,3,2})	152.89	1.15	0.16
338.512632	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,4,0} – 6 _{4,3,0})	145.33	1.15	0.18
338.512644	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,3,0} – 6 _{4,2,0})	145.33	1.15	0.18
338.512853	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,6,0} – 6 _{2,5,0})	102.70	1.57	0.37
338.530257	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,3,1} – 6 _{4,2,1})	160.99	1.15	0.15
338.540826	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,0} – 6 _{3,4,0})	114.79	1.39	0.29
338.543152	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,4,0} – 6 _{3,3,0})	114.79	1.39	0.29
338.559963	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,4,2} – 6 _{3,3,2})	127.71	1.40	0.26
338.583216	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,1} – 6 _{3,4,1})	112.71	1.39	0.30
338.611810	SO ₂	(20 _{1,19} – 19 _{2,18})	198.88	2.87	0.07
338.614936	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,6,1} – 6 _{1,5,1})	86.05	1.71	0.48
338.639802	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,0} – 6 _{2,4,0})	102.72	1.58	0.37
338.721693	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,6,1} – 6 _{2,5,1})	87.26	1.55	0.43
338.722898	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,2} – 6 _{2,4,2})	90.91	1.57	0.42
340.052575	C ³³ S	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	65.28	8.19	0.38
340.449273	OCS	(28 – 27)	236.95	1.15	0.06
340.714155	SO	(8 ₇ – 7 ₆)	81.25	4.99	0.12
341.415615	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,6,0} – 6 _{1,5,0})	80.09	1.71	0.50
342.729796	CH ₃ OH	(13 _{1,12,0} – 13 _{0,13,0})	227.47	4.23	0.51
342.882850	CS	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	65.83	8.40	–
344.200109	HC ¹⁵ N	(4 – 3)	41.30	18.80	0.05
344.310612	SO	(8 ₈ – 7 ₇)	87.48	5.19	0.13
345.338538	SO ₂	(13 _{2,12} – 12 _{1,11})	92.98	2.38	0.05
345.795990	CO	(3 – 2)	33.19	0.03	–
346.523878	SO ₂	(16 _{4,12} – 16 _{3,13})	164.47	3.39	0.07
346.528481	SO	(8 ₉ – 7 ₈)	78.78	5.38	0.16
346.652169	SO ₂	(19 _{1,19} – 18 _{0,18})	168.14	5.22	0.12
346.998344	H ¹³ CO ⁺	(4 – 3)	41.63	32.90	–
347.330581	SiO	(8 ₀ – 7 ₀)	75.02	22.00	0.03
348.534365	H ₂ CS	(10 _{1,9} – 9 _{1,8})	105.19	6.32	0.26
349.106997	CH ₃ OH	(14 _{1,13,0} – 14 _{0,14,0})	260.20	4.41	0.39

Table D.2. continued.

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4} [\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
349.212311	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{-6,0} – 18 _{6,0})	424.70	33.40	0.04
349.212311	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{6,0} – 18 _{-6,0})	424.70	33.40	0.04
349.286006	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{5,0} – 18 _{5,0})	346.22	34.60	0.05
349.346343	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{4,0} – 18 _{4,0})	281.99	35.50	0.07
349.393297	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{-3,0} – 18 _{3,0})	232.01	36.30	0.09
349.393297	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{3,0} – 18 _{-3,0})	232.01	36.30	0.09
349.426850	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{2,0} – 18 _{2,0})	196.30	36.80	0.10
349.446987	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{1,0} – 18 _{1,0})	174.88	37.10	0.12
349.453700	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{0,0} – 18 _{0,0})	167.74	37.20	0.12
350.687662	CH ₃ OH	(4 _{0,4,1} – 3 _{1,3,2})	36.34	0.87	0.22
350.905100	CH ₃ OH	(1 _{1,1,0} – 0 _{0,0,0})	16.84	3.32	0.35
351.768645	H ₂ CO	(5 _{1,5} – 4 _{1,4})	62.45	12.00	–
351.873873	SO ₂	(14 _{4,10} – 14 _{3,11})	135.87	3.43	0.07
352.599570	OCS	(29 – 28)	253.88	1.28	0.06
354.505477	HCN	(4 – 3)	42.53	20.50	–
355.602945	CH ₃ OH	(13 _{0,13,0} – 12 _{1,12,0})	211.03	2.53	0.33
356.007235	CH ₃ OH	(15 _{1,14,0} – 15 _{0,15,0})	295.26	4.60	0.30
356.734223	HCO ⁺	(4 – 3)	42.80	35.70	–
357.165390	SO ₂	(13 _{4,10} – 13 _{3,11})	122.97	3.51	0.06
357.241193	SO ₂	(15 _{4,12} – 15 _{3,13})	149.68	3.62	0.07
357.387579	SO ₂	(11 _{4,8} – 11 _{3,9})	99.95	3.38	0.06
357.581449	SO ₂	(8 _{4,4} – 8 _{3,5})	72.36	3.06	0.04
358.215633	SO ₂	(20 _{0,20} – 19 _{1,19})	185.33	5.83	0.12
358.605799	CH ₃ OH	(4 _{1,3,1} – 3 _{0,3,1})	44.26	1.32	0.30
359.151158	SO ₂	(25 _{3,23} – 25 _{2,24})	320.93	3.10	0.05
359.770685	SO ₂	(19 _{4,16} – 19 _{3,17})	214.26	3.85	0.07
360.848946	CH ₃ OH	(11 _{0,11,1} – 10 _{1,9,1})	166.05	1.21	0.21

Table D.3. Detected molecular transitions towards N63. The listed line transitions are from best fit line models obtained using the software package CASSIS, on the spectrum taken at the position of peak continuum emission. The model parameters are listed in Table 6 of the main text. Only transitions above 6 K are listed ($\sim 3\sigma$), corresponding to about 0.6 Jy beam⁻¹.

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4}[\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
329.330552	C ¹⁸ O	(3 – 2)	31.61	0.02	7.27
329.632881	CH ₃ OH	(12 _{2,10,0} – 11 _{3,9,0})	218.80	0.60	0.30
330.406503	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(16 _{2,15,1} – 15 _{1,14,1})	128.46	1.65	0.04
330.407010	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(49 _{10,40,3} – 48 _{11,37,3})	1256.39	0.20	0.00
330.463873	¹³ CH ₃ OH	(11 _{1,10,-0} – 11 _{0,11,+0})	165.27	3.90	0.08
330.464947	¹³ CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,+0} – 6 _{2,4,+0})	101.24	1.46	0.03
330.587965	¹³ CO	(3 – 2)	31.73	0.02	–
330.793887	CH ₃ OH	(8 _{3,5,2} – 9 _{2,7,2})	146.28	0.54	0.33
331.014296	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{-3,0} – 17 _{3,0})	215.24	30.70	0.06
331.014296	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{3,0} – 17 _{-3,0})	215.24	30.70	0.06
331.046096	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{2,0} – 17 _{2,0})	179.53	31.20	0.08
331.065182	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{1,0} – 17 _{1,0})	158.11	31.50	0.09
331.071544	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{0,0} – 17 _{0,0})	150.96	31.60	0.10
331.220371	CH ₃ OH	(16 _{1,16,2} – 15 _{2,13,2})	320.63	0.52	0.14
331.502319	CH ₃ OH	(11 _{1,10,0} – 11 _{0,11,0})	169.01	3.93	2.67
331.748518	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{-1,3} – 17 _{1,3})	670.28	31.40	0.06
331.992354	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{-2,2} – 17 _{2,2})	731.74	31.20	0.04
331.992354	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{2,2} – 17 _{-2,2})	731.74	31.20	0.04
332.015818	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{0,2} – 17 _{0,2})	676.58	31.60	0.06
332.017856	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{1,2} – 17 _{1,2})	697.02	31.50	0.05
332.028758	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{-4,3} – 17 _{4,3})	737.59	30.00	0.03
332.028758	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{4,3} – 17 _{-4,3})	737.59	30.00	0.03
332.129700	OC ³⁴ S	(28 – 27)	231.16	1.07	0.14
332.387753	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(18 _{1,3} – 17 _{-1,3})	670.57	31.60	0.06
333.448974	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{0,31,2} – 30 _{1,30,1})	259.59	0.82	0.00
333.448976	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{1,31,1} – 30 _{1,30,1})	259.59	5.73	0.02
333.448977	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{0,31,2} – 30 _{0,30,2})	259.59	5.73	0.02
333.448979	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{1,31,1} – 30 _{0,30,2})	259.59	0.82	0.00
333.449417	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{0,31,0} – 30 _{1,30,0})	259.57	0.91	0.00
333.449419	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{1,31,0} – 30 _{1,30,0})	259.57	5.64	0.02
333.449421	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{0,31,0} – 30 _{0,30,0})	259.57	5.64	0.02
333.449422	CH ₃ OCHO	(31 _{1,31,0} – 30 _{0,30,0})	259.57	0.91	0.00
333.449750	CH ₃ OCHO	(40 _{13,27,5} – 40 _{12,28,5})	782.89	0.53	0.00
335.133570	CH ₃ OH	(2 _{2,1,0} – 3 _{1,2,0})	44.67	0.27	0.11
335.395500	HDO	(3 _{3,1} – 4 _{2,2})	335.27	0.26	0.09
335.582017	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,7,0} – 6 _{1,6,0})	78.97	1.63	1.49
336.865149	CH ₃ OH	(12 _{1,11,0} – 12 _{0,12,0})	197.07	4.07	2.31
337.060513	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{1,5} – 2 _{2,5})	32.35	0.00	0.00
337.060709	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{0,5} – 2 _{1,5})	32.35	0.01	0.00
337.060831	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{2,5} – 2 _{3,5})	32.35	0.00	0.00
337.060936	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{2,5} – 2 _{2,5})	32.35	0.01	0.02
337.060988	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{4,5} – 2 _{3,5})	32.35	0.02	0.07
337.060988	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{5,5} – 2 _{4,5})	32.35	0.02	0.11
337.061050	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{1,5} – 2 _{1,5})	32.35	0.01	0.02
337.061123	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{3,5} – 2 _{3,5})	32.35	0.01	0.02
337.061214	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{0,5} – 2 _{0,5})	32.35	0.02	0.01
337.061226	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{3,5} – 2 _{2,5})	32.35	0.01	0.05
337.061471	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{2,5} – 2 _{1,5})	32.35	0.01	0.03
337.061553	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{1,5} – 2 _{0,5})	32.35	0.01	0.01
337.061951	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{4,5} – 2 _{4,5})	32.35	0.00	0.02
337.062093	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{3,5} – 2 _{4,5})	32.35	0.00	0.00
337.297484	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,7,3} – 6 _{1,6,3})	390.02	1.65	0.11
337.348660	CH ₂ DOH	(9 _{0,9,0} – 8 _{1,8,0})	96.28	1.46	0.05
337.396459	C ³⁴ S	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	64.77	8.00	0.24
337.580147	³⁴ SO	(8 ₈ – 7 ₇)	86.07	4.89	0.03
337.610661	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,5} – 6 _{3,4,5})	387.45	1.37	0.10

Table D.3. continued.

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4}[\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
337.610680	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{6,1,4} – 6 _{6,0,4})	657.12	0.43	0.00
337.625753	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,6,3} – 6 _{2,5,3})	363.50	1.55	0.13
337.635754	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,3} – 6 _{2,4,3})	363.50	1.55	0.13
337.642478	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,7,4} – 6 _{1,6,4})	356.30	1.65	0.15
337.643915	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,4} – 6 _{0,6,4})	365.40	1.69	0.14
337.646042	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,3,5} – 6 _{4,2,5})	470.22	1.14	0.04
337.655199	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,3} – 6 _{3,4,3})	460.94	1.38	0.05
337.655236	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,4,3} – 6 _{3,3,3})	460.94	1.38	0.05
337.969438	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,6,3} – 6 _{1,5,3})	390.15	1.66	0.11
338.083195	H ₂ CS	(10 _{1,10} – 9 _{1,9})	102.43	5.77	0.15
338.124488	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,1} – 6 _{0,6,1})	78.08	1.70	1.54
338.344588	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,7,2} – 6 _{1,6,2})	70.55	1.67	1.61
338.404610	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{6,2,1} – 6 _{6,1,1})	243.79	0.45	0.10
338.408698	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,0} – 6 _{0,6,0})	64.98	1.70	1.73
338.430975	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{6,1,2} – 6 _{6,0,2})	253.95	0.45	0.10
338.442367	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{6,1,0} – 6 _{6,0,0})	258.70	0.45	0.09
338.442367	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{6,2,0} – 6 _{6,1,0})	258.70	0.45	0.09
338.456536	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,3,2} – 6 _{5,2,2})	189.00	0.83	0.30
338.475226	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,2,1} – 6 _{5,1,1})	201.06	0.83	0.27
338.486322	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,2,0} – 6 _{5,1,0})	202.88	0.84	0.27
338.486322	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,3,0} – 6 _{5,2,0})	202.88	0.84	0.27
338.504065	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,4,2} – 6 _{4,3,2})	152.89	1.15	0.56
338.512632	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,4,0} – 6 _{4,3,0})	145.33	1.15	0.60
338.512644	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,3,0} – 6 _{4,2,0})	145.33	1.15	0.60
338.512853	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,6,0} – 6 _{2,5,0})	102.70	1.57	1.17
338.530257	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,3,1} – 6 _{4,2,1})	160.99	1.15	0.53
338.540826	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,0} – 6 _{3,4,0})	114.79	1.39	0.93
338.543152	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,4,0} – 6 _{3,3,0})	114.79	1.39	0.93
338.559963	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,4,2} – 6 _{3,3,2})	127.71	1.40	0.84
338.583216	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,1} – 6 _{3,4,1})	112.71	1.39	0.95
338.614936	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,6,1} – 6 _{1,5,1})	86.05	1.71	1.45
338.639802	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,0} – 6 _{2,4,0})	102.72	1.58	1.17
338.721693	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,6,1} – 6 _{2,5,1})	87.26	1.55	1.30
338.722898	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,2} – 6 _{2,4,2})	90.91	1.57	1.28
338.957114	CH ₂ DOH	(6 _{1,6,0} – 5 _{0,5,0})	48.42	1.59	0.05
338.957487	CH ₂ DOH	(23 _{2,21,0} – 22 _{3,19,2})	613.29	0.01	0.00
339.857269	³⁴ SO	(8 ₉ – 7 ₈)	77.34	5.08	0.04
340.141143	CH ₃ OH	(2 _{2,0,0} – 3 _{1,3,0})	44.67	0.28	0.11
340.449273	OCS	(28 – 27)	236.95	1.15	0.09
340.714155	SO	(8 ₇ – 7 ₆)	81.25	4.99	0.10
341.415615	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,6,0} – 6 _{1,5,0})	80.09	1.71	1.51
342.607898	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{0,19,3} – 18 _{1,18,3})	167.14	3.30	0.01
342.607898	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{0,19,5} – 18 _{1,18,5})	167.14	3.30	0.02
342.607971	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{0,19,1} – 18 _{1,18,1})	167.14	3.30	0.06
342.608044	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{0,19,0} – 18 _{1,18,0})	167.14	3.30	0.04
342.726474	CH ₃ OH	(20 _{6,15,5} – 19 _{7,13,5})	978.98	0.68	0.00
342.729796	CH ₃ OH	(13 _{1,12,0} – 13 _{0,13,0})	227.47	4.23	1.95
342.882850	CS	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	65.83	8.40	–
343.409963	H ₂ CS	(10 _{3,8} – 9 _{3,7})	209.10	5.56	0.07
343.414146	H ₂ CS	(10 _{3,7} – 9 _{3,6})	209.10	5.56	0.07
343.983268	OC ³⁴ S	(29 – 28)	247.67	1.19	0.12
344.029259	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{0,32,2} – 31 _{1,31,1})	276.10	0.77	0.00
344.029260	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{1,32,1} – 31 _{1,31,1})	276.10	6.43	0.02
344.029261	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{0,32,2} – 31 _{0,31,2})	276.10	6.43	0.02
344.029262	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{1,32,1} – 31 _{0,31,2})	276.10	0.77	0.00
344.029644	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{0,32,0} – 31 _{1,31,0})	276.08	1.00	0.00
344.029645	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{1,32,0} – 31 _{1,31,0})	276.08	6.20	0.02
344.029646	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{0,32,0} – 31 _{0,31,0})	276.08	6.20	0.02
344.029647	CH ₃ OCHO	(32 _{1,32,0} – 31 _{0,31,0})	276.08	1.00	0.00
344.200109	HC ¹⁵ N	(4 – 3)	41.30	18.80	0.07

Table D.3. continued.

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4}[\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
344.310612	SO	(8 ₈ – 7 ₇)	87.48	5.19	0.11
344.357816	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{1,19,3} – 18 _{0,18,3})	167.18	3.36	0.01
344.357816	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{1,19,5} – 18 _{0,18,5})	167.18	3.36	0.01
344.357826	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(38 _{4,35,3} – 38 _{3,36,3})	697.07	1.59	0.00
344.357826	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(38 _{4,35,5} – 38 _{3,36,5})	697.07	1.59	0.00
344.357929	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{1,19,1} – 18 _{0,18,1})	167.18	3.36	0.06
344.358041	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(19 _{1,19,0} – 18 _{0,18,0})	167.18	3.36	0.02
344.358087	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(38 _{4,35,1} – 38 _{3,36,1})	697.07	1.59	0.00
344.358347	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(38 _{4,35,0} – 38 _{3,36,0})	697.07	1.59	0.00
345.795990	CO	(3 – 2)	33.19	0.03	–
345.903916	CH ₃ OH	(16 _{1,15,0} – 15 _{2,14,0})	332.65	1.04	0.24
346.202719	CH ₃ OH	(5 _{4,2,0} – 6 _{3,3,0})	115.16	0.22	0.10
346.204271	CH ₃ OH	(5 _{4,1,0} – 6 _{3,4,0})	115.16	0.22	0.10
346.528481	SO	(8 ₉ – 7 ₈)	78.78	5.38	0.13
346.998344	H ¹³ CO ⁺	(4 – 3)	41.63	32.90	–
348.534365	H ₂ CS	(10 _{1,9} – 9 _{1,8})	105.19	6.32	0.16
349.106997	CH ₃ OH	(14 _{1,13,0} – 14 _{0,14,0})	260.20	4.41	1.60
349.393297	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{-3,0} – 18 _{3,0})	232.01	36.30	0.05
349.393297	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{3,0} – 18 _{-3,0})	232.01	36.30	0.05
349.426850	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{2,0} – 18 _{2,0})	196.30	36.80	0.07
349.446987	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{1,0} – 18 _{1,0})	174.88	37.10	0.09
349.453700	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{0,0} – 18 _{0,0})	167.74	37.20	0.10
350.168100	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{1,3} – 18 _{-1,3})	687.09	37.00	0.06
350.423619	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{-2,2} – 18 _{2,2})	748.55	36.80	0.04
350.423619	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{2,2} – 18 _{-2,2})	748.55	36.80	0.04
350.444906	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{0,2} – 18 _{0,2})	693.40	37.20	0.06
350.465645	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{-4,3} – 18 _{4,3})	754.41	35.60	0.03
350.465645	CH ₃ CN, v=0	(19 _{4,3} – 18 _{-4,3})	754.41	35.60	0.03
350.632072	CH ₂ DOH	(5 _{1,4,1} – 5 _{0,5,0})	48.98	2.07	0.05
350.687662	CH ₃ OH	(4 _{0,4,1} – 3 _{1,3,2})	36.34	0.87	0.63
350.842670	OC ³⁴ S	(19 _{-1,3} – 18 _{1,3})	687.41	37.20	0.06
350.905100	CH ₃ OH	(1 _{1,1,0} – 0 _{0,0,0})	16.84	3.32	0.94
351.236479	CH ₃ OH	(9 _{5,4,1} – 10 _{4,6,1})	240.51	0.36	0.10
351.768645	H ₂ CO	(5 _{1,5} – 4 _{1,4})	62.45	12.00	–
352.599570	OCS	(29 – 28)	253.88	1.28	0.08
352.801965	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{1,8,1} – 7 _{1,7,1})	92.69	1.78	0.05
353.732029	CH ₂ DOH	(6 _{1,5,1} – 6 _{0,6,0})	61.98	2.12	0.06
353.954518	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{1,8,2} – 7 _{1,7,2})	99.33	1.83	0.05
354.505477	HCN	(4 – 3)	42.53	20.50	–
354.607764	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{0,33,2} – 32 _{1,32,1})	293.12	0.70	0.00
354.607764	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{1,33,1} – 32 _{1,32,1})	293.12	7.19	0.02
354.607765	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{0,33,2} – 32 _{0,32,2})	293.12	7.19	0.02
354.607765	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{1,33,1} – 32 _{0,32,2})	293.12	0.70	0.00
354.608091	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{0,33,0} – 32 _{1,32,0})	293.10	1.10	0.00
354.608092	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{0,33,0} – 32 _{0,32,0})	293.10	6.79	0.02
354.608092	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{1,33,0} – 32 _{1,32,0})	293.10	6.79	0.02
354.608093	CH ₃ OCHO	(33 _{1,33,0} – 32 _{0,32,0})	293.10	1.10	0.00
355.292674	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{0,8,1} – 7 _{0,7,1})	90.37	1.80	0.05
355.602945	CH ₃ OH	(13 _{0,13,0} – 12 _{1,12,0})	211.03	2.53	1.24
355.835971	OC ³⁴ S	(30 – 29)	264.75	1.32	0.11
356.007235	CH ₃ OH	(15 _{1,14,0} – 15 _{0,15,0})	295.26	4.60	1.28
356.734223	HCO ⁺	(4 – 3)	42.80	35.70	–
356.899665	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{2,7,1} – 7 _{2,6,1})	103.67	1.80	0.05
356.932418	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{4,4,1} – 7 _{4,3,1})	149.21	1.41	0.03
356.932437	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{4,5,1} – 7 _{4,4,1})	149.21	1.41	0.03
356.973847	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{4,4,2} – 7 _{4,3,2})	159.18	1.41	0.03
356.973870	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{4,5,2} – 7 _{4,4,2})	159.18	1.41	0.03
356.978340	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{5,3,1} – 7 _{5,2,1})	185.14	1.09	0.02
356.978340	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{5,4,1} – 7 _{5,3,1})	185.14	1.09	0.02
356.981575	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{0,8,2} – 7 _{0,7,2})	95.45	1.77	0.05

Table D.3. continued.

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4} [\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
357.020783	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{3,6,2} – 7 _{3,5,2})	132.42	1.65	0.04
357.022008	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{3,5,2} – 7 _{3,4,2})	132.42	1.65	0.04
357.459408	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(18 _{2,17,3} – 17 _{1,16,3})	159.81	2.31	0.01
357.459408	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(18 _{2,17,5} – 17 _{1,16,5})	159.81	2.31	0.01
357.460164	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(18 _{2,17,1} – 17 _{1,16,1})	159.81	2.31	0.04
357.460920	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(18 _{2,17,0} – 17 _{1,16,0})	159.81	2.31	0.02
357.528563	CH ₂ DOH	(7 _{1,6,1} – 7 _{0,7,0})	77.13	2.18	0.06
357.687378	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{2,6,1} – 7 _{2,5,1})	103.77	1.81	0.05
358.449468	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(5 _{5,1,5} – 4 _{4,0,5})	48.80	3.71	0.01
358.449478	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(5 _{5,0,5} – 4 _{4,1,5})	48.80	3.71	0.02
358.451541	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(5 _{5,0,3} – 4 _{4,0,3})	48.80	3.71	0.01
358.452015	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(5 _{5,0,1} – 4 _{4,0,1})	48.80	3.71	0.05
358.454082	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(5 _{5,1,1} – 4 _{4,1,1})	48.80	3.71	0.05
358.456618	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(5 _{5,1,0} – 4 _{4,0,0})	48.80	3.71	0.02
358.456629	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(5 _{5,0,0} – 4 _{4,1,0})	48.80	3.71	0.03
358.605799	CH ₃ OH	(4 _{1,3,1} – 3 _{0,3,1})	44.26	1.32	0.85
359.753508	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{1,7,2} – 7 _{1,6,2})	100.59	1.93	0.05
360.584554	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(20 _{0,20,3} – 19 _{1,19,3})	184.48	3.89	0.01
360.584554	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(20 _{0,20,5} – 19 _{1,19,5})	184.48	3.89	0.01
360.584633	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(20 _{0,20,1} – 19 _{1,19,1})	184.48	3.89	0.05
360.584711	CH ₃ OCH ₃	(20 _{0,20,0} – 19 _{1,19,0})	184.48	3.89	0.02
360.661633	CH ₃ OH	(3 _{1,3,3} – 4 _{2,3,3})	339.14	2.64	0.11
360.734774	CH ₂ DOH	(8 _{1,7,1} – 7 _{1,6,1})	94.44	1.84	0.05
360.848946	CH ₃ OH	(11 _{0,11,1} – 10 _{1,9,1})	166.05	1.21	0.71

Table D.4. Detected molecular transitions towards N53. The listed line transitions are from best fit line models obtained using the software package CASSIS, on the spectrum taken at the position of peak continuum emission. The model parameters are listed in Table B.3. Only transitions above 6 K are listed ($\sim 3\sigma$), corresponding to about 0.6 Jy beam^{-1} .

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4} [\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
329.330552	C ¹⁸ O	(3 – 2)	31.61	0.02	–
330.587965	¹³ CO	(3 – 2)	31.73	0.02	–
331.502319	CH ₃ OH	(11 _{1,10,0} – 11 _{0,11,0})	169.01	3.93	0.38
335.582017	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,7,0} – 6 _{1,6,0})	78.97	1.63	0.18
336.865149	CH ₃ OH	(12 _{1,11,0} – 12 _{0,12,0})	197.07	4.07	0.34
337.060513	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{1,5} – 2 _{2,5})	32.35	0.00	0.00
337.060709	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{0,5} – 2 _{1,5})	32.35	0.01	0.00
337.060831	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{2,5} – 2 _{3,5})	32.35	0.00	0.00
337.060936	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{2,5} – 2 _{2,5})	32.35	0.01	0.02
337.060988	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{4,5} – 2 _{3,5})	32.35	0.02	0.07
337.060988	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{5,5} – 2 _{4,5})	32.35	0.02	0.11
337.061050	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{1,5} – 2 _{1,5})	32.35	0.01	0.02
337.061123	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{3,5} – 2 _{3,5})	32.35	0.01	0.02
337.061214	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{0,5} – 2 _{0,5})	32.35	0.02	0.01
337.061226	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{3,5} – 2 _{2,5})	32.35	0.01	0.05
337.061471	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{2,5} – 2 _{1,5})	32.35	0.01	0.03
337.061553	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{1,5} – 2 _{0,5})	32.35	0.01	0.01
337.061951	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{4,5} – 2 _{4,5})	32.35	0.00	0.02
337.062093	C ¹⁷ O	(3 _{3,5} – 2 _{4,5})	32.35	0.00	0.00
337.396459	C ³⁴ S	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	64.77	8.00	0.21
337.642478	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,7,4} – 6 _{1,6,4})	356.30	1.65	0.03
337.643915	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,4} – 6 _{0,6,4})	365.40	1.69	0.03
338.124488	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,1} – 6 _{0,6,1})	78.08	1.70	0.19
338.344588	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,7,2} – 6 _{1,6,2})	70.55	1.67	0.19
338.408698	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{0,7,0} – 6 _{0,6,0})	64.98	1.70	0.21
338.486322	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,2,0} – 6 _{5,1,0})	202.88	0.84	0.04
338.486322	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{5,3,0} – 6 _{5,2,0})	202.88	0.84	0.04
338.504065	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,4,2} – 6 _{4,3,2})	152.89	1.15	0.08
338.512632	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,4,0} – 6 _{4,3,0})	145.33	1.15	0.08
338.512644	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,3,0} – 6 _{4,2,0})	145.33	1.15	0.08
338.512853	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,6,0} – 6 _{2,5,0})	102.70	1.57	0.15
338.530257	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{4,3,1} – 6 _{4,2,1})	160.99	1.15	0.07
338.540826	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,0} – 6 _{3,4,0})	114.79	1.39	0.12
338.543152	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,4,0} – 6 _{3,3,0})	114.79	1.39	0.12
338.559963	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,4,2} – 6 _{3,3,2})	127.71	1.40	0.11
338.583216	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{3,5,1} – 6 _{3,4,1})	112.71	1.39	0.12
338.614936	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,6,1} – 6 _{1,5,1})	86.05	1.71	0.18
338.639802	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,0} – 6 _{2,4,0})	102.72	1.58	0.15
338.721693	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,6,1} – 6 _{2,5,1})	87.26	1.55	0.16
338.722898	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{2,5,2} – 6 _{2,4,2})	90.91	1.57	0.16
340.052575	C ³³ S	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	65.28	8.19	0.09
340.714155	SO	(8 ₇ – 7 ₆)	81.25	4.99	0.13
341.415615	CH ₃ OH	(7 _{1,6,0} – 6 _{1,5,0})	80.09	1.71	0.18
342.726474	CH ₃ OH	(20 _{6,15,5} – 19 _{7,13,5})	978.98	0.68	0.00
342.729796	CH ₃ OH	(13 _{1,12,0} – 13 _{0,13,0})	227.47	4.23	0.30
342.882850	CS	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	65.83	8.40	–
344.310612	SO	(8 ₈ – 7 ₇)	87.48	5.19	0.14
345.795990	CO	(3 – 2)	33.19	0.03	–
346.528481	SO	(8 ₉ – 7 ₈)	78.78	5.38	0.17
349.106997	CH ₃ OH	(14 _{1,13,0} – 14 _{0,14,0})	260.20	4.41	0.26
350.687662	CH ₃ OH	(4 _{0,4,1} – 3 _{1,3,2})	36.34	0.87	0.07
350.905100	CH ₃ OH	(1 _{1,1,0} – 0 _{0,0,0})	16.84	3.32	0.10
351.768645	H ₂ CO	(5 _{1,5} – 4 _{1,4})	62.45	12.00	–
354.505477	HCN	(4 – 3)	42.53	20.50	–
355.602945	CH ₃ OH	(13 _{0,13,0} – 12 _{1,12,0})	211.03	2.53	0.19
356.007235	CH ₃ OH	(15 _{1,14,0} – 15 _{0,15,0})	295.26	4.60	0.22
356.734223	HCO ⁺	(4 – 3)	42.80	35.70	–

Table D.4. continued.

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4}[\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
358.605799	CH ₃ OH	(4 _{1,3,1} – 3 _{0,3,1})	44.26	1.32	0.10
360.848946	CH ₃ OH	(11 _{0,11,1} – 10 _{1,9,1})	166.05	1.21	0.10

Table D.5. Detected molecular transitions towards N54. The listed line transitions are from best fit line models obtained using the software package CASSIS, on the spectrum taken at the position of peak continuum emission. The model parameters are listed in Table B.4. Only transitions above 6 K are listed ($\sim 3\sigma$), corresponding to about 0.6 Jy beam^{-1} .

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4} [\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
330.587965	^{13}CO	(3 – 2)	31.73	0.02	–
342.882850	CS	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	65.83	8.40	–
345.795990	CO	(3 – 2)	33.19	0.03	–
351.768645	H ₂ CO	(5 _{1,5} – 4 _{1,4})	62.45	12.00	–
354.505477	HCN	(4 – 3)	42.53	20.50	–
356.734223	HCO ⁺	(4 – 3)	42.80	35.70	–

Table D.6. Detected molecular transitions towards N51. The listed line transitions are from best fit line models obtained using the software package CASSIS, on the spectrum taken at the position of peak continuum emission. The model parameters are listed in Table B.5. Only transitions above 6 K are listed ($\sim 3\sigma$), corresponding to about 0.6 Jy beam^{-1} .

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4} [\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
330.587965	^{13}CO	(3 – 2)	31.73	0.02	–
331.502319	CH_3OH	(11 _{1,10,0} – 11 _{0,11,0})	169.01	3.93	0.19
335.582017	CH_3OH	(7 _{1,7,0} – 6 _{1,6,0})	78.97	1.63	0.09
336.865149	CH_3OH	(12 _{1,11,0} – 12 _{0,12,0})	197.07	4.07	0.17
338.124488	CH_3OH	(7 _{0,7,1} – 6 _{0,6,1})	78.08	1.70	0.09
338.344588	CH_3OH	(7 _{1,7,2} – 6 _{1,6,2})	70.55	1.67	0.10
338.408698	CH_3OH	(7 _{0,7,0} – 6 _{0,6,0})	64.98	1.70	0.10
338.512632	CH_3OH	(7 _{4,4,0} – 6 _{4,3,0})	145.33	1.15	0.04
338.512644	CH_3OH	(7 _{4,3,0} – 6 _{4,2,0})	145.33	1.15	0.04
338.512853	CH_3OH	(7 _{2,6,0} – 6 _{2,5,0})	102.70	1.57	0.07
338.540826	CH_3OH	(7 _{3,5,0} – 6 _{3,4,0})	114.79	1.39	0.06
338.543152	CH_3OH	(7 _{3,4,0} – 6 _{3,3,0})	114.79	1.39	0.06
338.559963	CH_3OH	(7 _{3,4,2} – 6 _{3,3,2})	127.71	1.40	0.06
338.583216	CH_3OH	(7 _{3,5,1} – 6 _{3,4,1})	112.71	1.39	0.06
338.614936	CH_3OH	(7 _{1,6,1} – 6 _{1,5,1})	86.05	1.71	0.09
338.639802	CH_3OH	(7 _{2,5,0} – 6 _{2,4,0})	102.72	1.58	0.07
338.721693	CH_3OH	(7 _{2,6,1} – 6 _{2,5,1})	87.26	1.55	0.08
338.722898	CH_3OH	(7 _{2,5,2} – 6 _{2,4,2})	90.91	1.57	0.08
340.714155	SO	(8 ₇ – 7 ₆)	81.25	4.99	0.10
341.415615	CH_3OH	(7 _{1,6,0} – 6 _{1,5,0})	80.09	1.71	0.09
342.729796	CH_3OH	(13 _{1,12,0} – 13 _{0,13,0})	227.47	4.23	0.15
342.882850	CS	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	65.83	8.40	–
344.310612	SO	(8 ₈ – 7 ₇)	87.48	5.19	0.11
345.795990	CO	(3 – 2)	33.19	0.03	–
346.528481	SO	(8 ₉ – 7 ₈)	78.78	5.38	0.13
349.106997	CH_3OH	(14 _{1,13,0} – 14 _{0,14,0})	260.20	4.41	0.13
350.905100	CH_3OH	(1 _{1,1,0} – 0 _{0,0,0})	16.84	3.32	0.05
351.768645	H_2CO	(5 _{1,5} – 4 _{1,4})	62.45	12.00	–
354.505477	HCN	(4 – 3)	42.53	20.50	–
355.602945	CH_3OH	(13 _{0,13,0} – 12 _{1,12,0})	211.03	2.53	0.09
356.007235	CH_3OH	(15 _{1,14,0} – 15 _{0,15,0})	295.26	4.60	0.11
356.734223	HCO^+	(4 – 3)	42.80	35.70	–
358.605799	CH_3OH	(4 _{1,3,1} – 3 _{0,3,1})	44.26	1.32	0.05
360.848946	CH_3OH	(11 _{0,11,1} – 10 _{1,9,1})	166.05	1.21	0.05

Table D.7. Detected molecular transitions towards N38. The listed line transitions are from best fit line models obtained using the software package CASSIS, on the spectrum taken at the position of peak continuum emission. The model parameters are listed in Table B.6. Only transitions above 6 K are listed ($\sim 3\sigma$), corresponding to about 0.6 Jy beam^{-1} .

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4} [\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
330.587965	^{13}CO	(3 – 2)	31.73	0.02	–
331.502319	CH_3OH	(11 _{1,10,0} – 11 _{0,11,0})	169.01	3.93	0.38
335.582017	CH_3OH	(7 _{1,7,0} – 6 _{1,6,0})	78.97	1.63	0.18
336.865149	CH_3OH	(12 _{1,11,0} – 12 _{0,12,0})	197.07	4.07	0.34
337.642478	CH_3OH	(7 _{1,7,4} – 6 _{1,6,4})	356.30	1.65	0.03
337.643915	CH_3OH	(7 _{0,7,4} – 6 _{0,6,4})	365.40	1.69	0.03
338.083195	H_2CS	(10 _{1,10} – 9 _{1,9})	102.43	5.77	0.15
338.124488	CH_3OH	(7 _{0,7,1} – 6 _{0,6,1})	78.08	1.70	0.19
338.344588	CH_3OH	(7 _{1,7,2} – 6 _{1,6,2})	70.55	1.67	0.19
338.408698	CH_3OH	(7 _{0,7,0} – 6 _{0,6,0})	64.98	1.70	0.21
338.486322	CH_3OH	(7 _{5,2,0} – 6 _{5,1,0})	202.88	0.84	0.04
338.486322	CH_3OH	(7 _{5,3,0} – 6 _{5,2,0})	202.88	0.84	0.04
338.504065	CH_3OH	(7 _{4,4,2} – 6 _{4,3,2})	152.89	1.15	0.08
338.512632	CH_3OH	(7 _{4,4,0} – 6 _{4,3,0})	145.33	1.15	0.08
338.512644	CH_3OH	(7 _{4,3,0} – 6 _{4,2,0})	145.33	1.15	0.08
338.512853	CH_3OH	(7 _{2,6,0} – 6 _{2,5,0})	102.70	1.57	0.15
338.530257	CH_3OH	(7 _{4,3,1} – 6 _{4,2,1})	160.99	1.15	0.07
338.540826	CH_3OH	(7 _{3,5,0} – 6 _{3,4,0})	114.79	1.39	0.12
338.543152	CH_3OH	(7 _{3,4,0} – 6 _{3,3,0})	114.79	1.39	0.12
338.559963	CH_3OH	(7 _{3,4,2} – 6 _{3,3,2})	127.71	1.40	0.11
338.583216	CH_3OH	(7 _{3,5,1} – 6 _{3,4,1})	112.71	1.39	0.12
338.614936	CH_3OH	(7 _{1,6,1} – 6 _{1,5,1})	86.05	1.71	0.18
338.639802	CH_3OH	(7 _{2,5,0} – 6 _{2,4,0})	102.72	1.58	0.15
338.721693	CH_3OH	(7 _{2,6,1} – 6 _{2,5,1})	87.26	1.55	0.16
338.722898	CH_3OH	(7 _{2,5,2} – 6 _{2,4,2})	90.91	1.57	0.16
340.714155	SO	(8 ₇ – 7 ₆)	81.25	4.99	0.05
341.415615	CH_3OH	(7 _{1,6,0} – 6 _{1,5,0})	80.09	1.71	0.18
342.726474	CH_3OH	(20 _{6,15,5} – 19 _{7,13,5})	978.98	0.68	0.00
342.729796	CH_3OH	(13 _{1,12,0} – 13 _{0,13,0})	227.47	4.23	0.30
342.882850	CS	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	65.83	8.40	–
344.310612	SO	(8 ₈ – 7 ₇)	87.48	5.19	0.05
345.795990	CO	(3 – 2)	33.19	0.03	–
346.528481	SO	(8 ₉ – 7 ₈)	78.78	5.38	0.06
348.534365	H_2CS	(10 _{1,9} – 9 _{1,8})	105.19	6.32	0.15
349.106997	CH_3OH	(14 _{1,13,0} – 14 _{0,14,0})	260.20	4.41	0.26
350.687662	CH_3OH	(4 _{0,4,1} – 3 _{1,3,2})	36.34	0.87	0.07
350.905100	CH_3OH	(1 _{1,1,0} – 0 _{0,0,0})	16.84	3.32	0.10
351.768645	H_2CO	(5 _{1,5} – 4 _{1,4})	62.45	12.00	–
354.505477	HCN	(4 – 3)	42.53	20.50	–
355.602945	CH_3OH	(13 _{0,13,0} – 12 _{1,12,0})	211.03	2.53	0.19
356.007235	CH_3OH	(15 _{1,14,0} – 15 _{0,15,0})	295.26	4.60	0.22
356.734223	HCO^+	(4 – 3)	42.80	35.70	–
358.605799	CH_3OH	(4 _{1,3,1} – 3 _{0,3,1})	44.26	1.32	0.10
360.848946	CH_3OH	(11 _{0,11,1} – 10 _{1,9,1})	166.05	1.21	0.10

Table D.8. Detected molecular transitions towards N48. The listed line transitions are from best fit line models obtained using the software package CASSIS, on the spectrum taken at the position of peak continuum emission. The model parameters are listed in Table B.7. Only transitions above 6 K are listed ($\sim 3\sigma$), corresponding to about 0.6 Jy beam^{-1} .

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4} [\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
330.587965	^{13}CO	(3 – 2)	31.73	0.02	–
331.502319	CH_3OH	(11 _{1,10,0} – 11 _{0,11,0})	169.01	3.93	0.19
335.582017	CH_3OH	(7 _{1,7,0} – 6 _{1,6,0})	78.97	1.63	0.09
336.865149	CH_3OH	(12 _{1,11,0} – 12 _{0,12,0})	197.07	4.07	0.17
338.124488	CH_3OH	(7 _{0,7,1} – 6 _{0,6,1})	78.08	1.70	0.09
338.344588	CH_3OH	(7 _{1,7,2} – 6 _{1,6,2})	70.55	1.67	0.10
338.408698	CH_3OH	(7 _{0,7,0} – 6 _{0,6,0})	64.98	1.70	0.10
338.512632	CH_3OH	(7 _{4,4,0} – 6 _{4,3,0})	145.33	1.15	0.04
338.512644	CH_3OH	(7 _{4,3,0} – 6 _{4,2,0})	145.33	1.15	0.04
338.512853	CH_3OH	(7 _{2,6,0} – 6 _{2,5,0})	102.70	1.57	0.07
338.540826	CH_3OH	(7 _{3,5,0} – 6 _{3,4,0})	114.79	1.39	0.06
338.543152	CH_3OH	(7 _{3,4,0} – 6 _{3,3,0})	114.79	1.39	0.06
338.559963	CH_3OH	(7 _{3,4,2} – 6 _{3,3,2})	127.71	1.40	0.06
338.583216	CH_3OH	(7 _{3,5,1} – 6 _{3,4,1})	112.71	1.39	0.06
338.614936	CH_3OH	(7 _{1,6,1} – 6 _{1,5,1})	86.05	1.71	0.09
338.639802	CH_3OH	(7 _{2,5,0} – 6 _{2,4,0})	102.72	1.58	0.07
338.721693	CH_3OH	(7 _{2,6,1} – 6 _{2,5,1})	87.26	1.55	0.08
338.722898	CH_3OH	(7 _{2,5,2} – 6 _{2,4,2})	90.91	1.57	0.08
340.714155	SO	(8 ₇ – 7 ₆)	81.25	4.99	0.05
341.415615	CH_3OH	(7 _{1,6,0} – 6 _{1,5,0})	80.09	1.71	0.09
342.729796	CH_3OH	(13 _{1,12,0} – 13 _{0,13,0})	227.47	4.23	0.15
342.882850	CS	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	65.83	8.40	–
344.310612	SO	(8 ₈ – 7 ₇)	87.48	5.19	0.05
345.795990	CO	(3 – 2)	33.19	0.03	–
346.528481	SO	(8 ₉ – 7 ₈)	78.78	5.38	0.06
349.106997	CH_3OH	(14 _{1,13,0} – 14 _{0,14,0})	260.20	4.41	0.13
350.905100	CH_3OH	(1 _{1,1,0} – 0 _{0,0,0})	16.84	3.32	0.05
351.768645	H_2CO	(5 _{1,5} – 4 _{1,4})	62.45	12.00	–
354.505477	HCN	(4 – 3)	42.53	20.50	–
355.602945	CH_3OH	(13 _{0,13,0} – 12 _{1,12,0})	211.03	2.53	0.09
356.007235	CH_3OH	(15 _{1,14,0} – 15 _{0,15,0})	295.26	4.60	0.11
356.734223	HCO^+	(4 – 3)	42.80	35.70	–
358.605799	CH_3OH	(4 _{1,3,1} – 3 _{0,3,1})	44.26	1.32	0.05
360.848946	CH_3OH	(11 _{0,11,1} – 10 _{1,9,1})	166.05	1.21	0.05

Table D.9. Detected molecular transitions towards S8. The listed line transitions are from best fit line models obtained using the software package CASSIS, on the spectrum taken at the position of peak continuum emission. The model parameters are listed in Table B.8. Only transitions above 6 K are listed ($\sim 3\sigma$), corresponding to about 0.6 Jy beam^{-1} .

Frequency [GHz]	Molecule	Transition	$E_{\text{up}}/k_{\text{B}}$ [K]	A_{ij} $\times 10^{-4} [\text{s}^{-1}]$	Opacity (τ)
330.587965	^{13}CO	(3 – 2)	31.73	0.02	–
340.714155	SO	(8 ₇ – 7 ₆)	81.25	4.99	0.05
342.882850	CS	(7 ₀ – 6 ₀)	65.83	8.40	–
344.310612	SO	(8 ₈ – 7 ₇)	87.48	5.19	0.05
345.795990	CO	(3 – 2)	33.19	0.03	–
346.528481	SO	(8 ₉ – 7 ₈)	78.78	5.38	0.06
351.768645	H ₂ CO	(5 _{1,5} – 4 _{1,4})	62.45	12.00	–
354.505477	HCN	(4 – 3)	42.53	20.50	–
356.734223	HCO ⁺	(4 – 3)	42.80	35.70	–